

A systematic and synonymic list of the Riodinidae and the Lycaenidae (part 1) of Western Palearctic butterflies hyperlinked to the original descriptions (Lepidoptera, Papilionoidea)

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Abstract

A systematic and synonymic list of the Riodinidae and the Lycaenidae (part I) butterflies of the Western Palearctic is presented, with all names hyperlinked to their original descriptions. The work covers taxonomic hierarchy from family to species level, incorporating historical synonyms, typification details, and bibliographic references, providing a comprehensive and navigable tool for lepidopterists and taxonomists.

Key words

Lepidoptera — Papilionoidea — Riodinidae — Nemeobinae — Lycaenidae — Aphnaeinae — Lycaeninae — Theclinae — Western Palearctic — taxonomy — nomenclature — synonymy — systematic catalogue — type species — original descriptions — type locality — butterfly classification — historical entomology.

Introduction

The present paper deals with the classification of the West Palearctic representatives of the families *Riodinidae* and *Lycaenidae*, with particular emphasis on the subfamily *Nemeobiinae* and on three subfamilies of *Lycaenidae*: *Aphnaeinae*, *Lycaeninae* and *Theclinae*. Within the West Palearctic fauna, *Nemeobiinae* is represented by a single species only, whereas *Lycaenidae* comprises a considerably larger number of taxa and several additional subfamilies. Owing to this diversity, the remaining West Palearctic subfamilies of *Lycaenidae* will be treated separately in subsequent papers.

The habitus generally allows an easy identification of most species included in these groups. However, the examination of genitalia remains necessary in certain cases, particularly within the genus *Callophrys*, or for distinguishing closely related taxa such as *Lycaena candens* and *L. hippothoe*.

Despite the considerable progress achieved in recent years, several taxonomic and systematic problems still remain unresolved. Further phylogenetic studies will be required to clarify the specific or subspecific status of several taxa and to provide a more satisfactory generic arrangement, especially within the tribes *Lycaenini* and *Eumaeini*. Since these groups include closely related species occurring in both the Palearctic and Nearctic regions, future studies should adopt a comprehensive approach including taxa from the entire Holarctic region in order to achieve a more stable and natural classification.

Several species groups continue to present substantial taxonomic difficulties, and the status of some taxa remains uncertain, whether they should be regarded as distinct species, subspecies, or evolutionary significant units (ESUs). This uncertainty applies, for example, to taxa such as *Lycaena heracleana*, *Cigaritis estherae* and *Satyrium vandalousica*.

Regular updates to a comprehensive systematic and synonymic reference list are therefore essential. A dynamic, continuously maintained list offers clear advantages over fixed, paper-based publications, which cannot be revised once issued and may become outdated relatively quickly as new taxonomic insights emerge.

Family

Riodinidae Grote, 1895

[ORIG] Riodinidae Grote, 1895. Mitt. Roemer Mus. Hildesheim (1): [\[2\]](#), [\[4\]](#).

TG: *Riodina* Westwood, 1851.

[JH] Erycinidae Swainson, 1827. Phil. Mag. (2)1(3): [185](#).

TG: *Erycina* Fabricius, 1807. Mag. Insektenk. 6: [286](#), nec *Erycina* Lamarck, 1805. Ann. Mus. Hist. Nat. 6: [413](#).

Subfamily

Nemeobiinae Bates, 1868

- [ORIG] Nemeobiinae Bates, 1868. J. Linn. Soc., Zool. 9: [412](#).
TG: *Nemeobius* Stephens, 1827 (= *Hamearis* Hübner, [1819]).
- [JS] Hamearinae Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [299](#).
TG: *Hamearis* Hübner, [1819].

Tribe

Nemeobiini Bates, 1868

- [ORIG] Nemeobiinae Bates, 1868. J. Linn. Soc., Zool. 9: [412](#).
TG: *Nemeobius* Stephens, 1827 (= *Hamearis* Hübner, [1819]).
- [JS] Hamearinae Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [299](#).
TG: *Hamearis* Hübner, [1819].

Genus

Hamearis Hübner, [1819]

- [ORIG] *Hamearis* Hübner, [1819]. Verz. bekannt. Schmett.: [19](#).
TS: *Papilio lucina* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation by Curtis, 1830. Brit. Entomol. 5: [no. 316](#).
- [JS] *Nemeobius* Stephens, 1827. Illustr. Brit. Entomol. (Haustellata) 1(4): [28-29](#).
TS: *Papilio lucina* Linnaeus, 1758 by monotypy.

Hamearis lucina (Linnaeus, 1758)

- [ORIG] *Papilio lucina* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [480](#).
TL: S England.
- [IFS] *Nemeobius lucina* ab. *primipara* Costantini, 1916. Atti Soc. Nat. Mat. Modena (5)3: [15](#).
TL: Monte Gibbio (Modena prov., Italy).
- [JS] *Nemeobius lucina* f. *semibrunnea* Vorbrodt, 1917. In: Vorbrodt & Müller-Rutz, Mitt. Schweiz. Entomol. Ges. 12(9-10): [443](#).
TL: Geneva (W Switzerland).
- [JS] *Nemeobius lucina* f. *fulvior* Rocci, 1923. Mem. Soc. Entomol. Ital. 2: [6-7](#).
TL: Piedmont (NW Italy).
- [JS] *Nemeobius lucina* var. *browni* Oberthür, 1923. In: Lhomme, Cat. Lépid. Fr. Belg.: 72.
TL: Cadaujac (Gironde, France).
- [JS] *Nemeobius lucina* race *praestans* Verity, 1923. In: Verity & Querci, Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 35(suppl.): [13](#).
TL: Vingone Valley, Florence (Tuscany, Italy).
- [JS] *Nemeobius lucina* race *parvifulvior* Verity, 1923. In: Verity & Querci, Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 35(suppl.): [14](#).
TL: Belstead Wood, Ipswich (Suffolk, UK).
- [JS] *Nemeobius lucina* race *thurneri* Dannehl, 1925. Entomol. Z. 39(2): [6](#).
TL: Karawanks (Carinthia, Austria).
- [JS] *Nemeobius lucina* var. *sorini* Pionneau, 1926. Échange 42(424): 7.
TL: Gèdre (Hautes-Pyrénées dep., S France).

[SN] *Hamearis lucina* race *primipara* Verity, 1943. Farfalle diurne Italia 2: 390-381.
Comb. nov. and Stat. nov. for *Nemeobius lucina* ab. *primipara* Costantini, 1916.

Family

Lycaenidae [Leach], [1815]

[ORIG] Lycaenida [Leach], [1815]. In: Brewster, Edinburgh Ency. 9(1): [129](#).

TG: *Lycaena* Fabricius, 1807.

[JH] Lycaenides Herrich-Schäffer, [1843]. Syst. Bearb. Schmett. Eur. 1(1): [16](#).

TG: *Lycaena* Fabricius, 1807.

Subfamily

Aphnaeinae Distant, [1884]

[ORIG] Aphnaria Distant, [1884]. Rhopal. Malanaya: [196](#), [233](#).

TG: *Aphnaeus* Hübner, [1819].

Tribe

Aphnaeini Distant, [1884]

[ORIG] Aphnaria Distant, [1884]. Rhopal. Malanaya: [196](#), [233](#).

TG: *Aphnaeus* Hübner, [1819].

Genus

Cigaritis Donzel, 1847

[ORIG] *Cigaritis* Donzel, 1847. Ann. Soc. entomol. Fr. (2)5: [528](#).

TS: *Cigaritis zohra* Donzel, 1847 by subsequent designation by Scudder, 1875. Proc. Am. Acad. Arts Sci. 10(2): [142](#).

[JH] *Zerythis* Lucas, 1849. Explor. Sci. Algérie, Zool. 3: [pl. 1, fig. 8](#).

TS: *Zerythis siphax* Lucas, 1849 by monotypy ; *nec Zerythis* Blanchard, 1840. Hist. Nat. Ins. 3: 463.

[JS] *Spindasis* Wallengren, 1857. Kongl. Svenska Vetensk.-Akad. Handl. (NF)2(4): [45](#).

TS: *Spindasis masilikazi* Wallengren, 1857 by original designation.

[JS] *Apharitis* Riley, 1925. Novit. Zool. 32: [78-79](#).

TS: *Polyommatus epargyros* Eversmann, 1854 by original designation.

Cigaritis zohra Donzel, 1847

[ORIG] *Cigaritis zohra* Donzel, 1847. Ann. Soc. entomol. Fr. (2)5: [528-529](#), [pl. 8, fig. 5-6](#).

TL: Algeria.

[JS] *Cigaritis* var. *jugurtha* Oberthür, 1876. Étud. Entomol. 1: [21](#).

TL: Saïda (Algeria).

[JS] *Cigaritis massinissa* Lucas, 1849. Explor. Sci. Algérie, Zool. 3: [364-365](#).

TL: Djebel Amour (Algeria).

- [JS] *Cigaritis zohra* ssp. *littoralis* Riley, 1925. Novit. Zool. 32: [75](#).
TL: Oran (Algeria).
- [JS] *Cigaritis zohra* ssp. *guercifi* Gallet, 2003. Linneana Belgica 19(3): [129-130, fig.](#)
TL: Guercif, Taza (N Morocco).
- [JS] *Cigaritis zohra* ssp. *cryptozohra* Tarrier & André, 2016. Alexanor 27(6): [364-367, fig.](#)
TL: Tizi-n-Taghatine, SE Taliouine (Anti-Atlas, Morocco).

***Cigaritis monticola* Riley, 1925**

- [ORIG] *Cigaritis zohra* ssp. *monticola* Riley, 1925. Entomologist 58: 270.
TL: Taghzeft Pass, Aghbalu Larbi (Morocco).
- [JS] *Cigaritis monticola* ssp. *micromonticola* Tarrier, 2019. Alexanor 28(7-8): [657-658, fig.](#)
TL: Tizi-n-Tamda, NE Ali-Mhammed (High Atlas, Morocco).

***Cigaritis allardi* Oberthür, 1909**

- [ORIG] *Cigaritis allardi* Oberthür, 1909. Étud. Lépid. comp. 3: [401-403](#).
TL: Sebdou (Tlemcen prov., Algeria).
- [JS] *Cigaritis allardi* ssp. *occidentalis* Le Cerf, 1923. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 28(15): [197-198](#).
TL: Aïn El-Harcha (Morocco).
- [JS] *Cigaritis allardi* ssp. *meridionalis* Riley, 1925. Novit. Zool. 32: [72](#).
TL: Djebel Mekter (Algeria).
- [JS] *Cigaritis allardi* ssp. *neomeridionalis* Tarrier, 2025. Gen. Cigaritis Morocco: [38, fig.](#)
TL: Tizi-n-Ouguerd-Zegzaoune (High Atlas, Morocco).

ESU *C. estherae* Brévignon, 1985

- [ORIG] *Cigaritis allardi* ssp. *estherae* Brévignon, 1985. Alexanor 13(7): 307-308, fig.
TL: Agadir (Morocco).

***Cigaritis siphax* Lucas, 1849**

- [ORIG] *Cigaritis siphax* Lucas, 1849. Explor. Scient. Algérie, Hist. nat. Anim. articul. 3: [362-363](#), pl. 1, [fig. 8a-c](#).
TL: Constantine (Algeria).
- [JS] *Cigaritis siphax* ab.(var.) *erythrea* Staudinger, 1892. Dt. Entomol. Z. 5(2): [280](#).
TL: Tunis (Tunisia).
- [JS] *Cigaritis zohra* ssp. *orientalis* Riley, 1925. Novit. Zool. 32: [76](#).
TL: Ksar El Boukhari (Algeria).

***Cigaritis myrmecophila* Dumont, 1922**

- [ORIG] *Cigaritis myrmecophila* Dumont, 1922. Bull. Soc. entomol. Fr. 1922(15): [217-218](#).
TL: Tozeur, Nefta (Tunisia).

Cigaritis acamas (Klug, 1834)

- [ORIG] *Lycaena acamas* Klug, 1834. Symb. Phys., Ins. 4: [\[40\]](#), [pl. 40, fig. 7](#).
TL: Syria.
- [JS] *Cigaritis acamas* var. *obscurata* Staudinger, 1901. In: Staudinger & Rebel, Cat. Lepid. pal. Faunengeb.: [76](#).
TL: Hadjin, Taurus (Turkey).
- [JS] *Apharitis acamas* ssp. *egyptiaca* Riley, 1925. Novit. Zool. 32: [88](#).
TL: Mokkatam Hills (Egypt).
- [JS] *Apharitis acamas* ssp. *cypriaca* Riley, 1925. Novit. Zool. 32: [89](#).
TL: Episkopis (Cyprus).
- [JS] *Cigaritis acamas* ssp. *dueldueli* Pfeiffer, 1932. Mitt. Munch. Entomol. Ges. 22(1): [38](#).
TL: Amanus Mts, Düldül Dagi (Turkey).

Subfamily

Lycaeninae [Leach], [1815]

- [ORIG] Lycaenida [Leach], [1815]. In: Brewster, Edinburgh Ency. 9(1): [129](#).
TG: *Lycaena* Fabricius, 1807.
- [JH] Lycaenides Herrich-Schäffer, [1843]. Syst. Bearb. Schmett. Eur. 1(1): [16](#).
TG: *Lycaena* Fabricius, 1807.

Tribe

Lycaenini [Leach], [1815]

- [ORIG] Lycaenida [Leach], [1815]. In: Brewster, Edinburgh Ency. 9(1): [129](#).
TG: *Lycaena* Fabricius, 1807.
- [JS] Lycaenides Herrich-Schäffer, [1843]. Syst. Bearb. Schmett. Eur. 1(1): [16](#).
TG: *Lycaena* Fabricius, 1807.
- [RJ] Chrysophanidi Scudder, 1889. Butt. east U.S. & Canada 2: [793](#).
TG: *Chrysophanus* Hübner, 1818 ; rejected by Opinion 541 (ICZN, 1959).

Genus

Lycaena Fabricius, 1807

- [ORIG] *Lycaena* Fabricius, 1807. In: Illiger, Mag. Insektenk. 6: [285-286](#).
TS: *Papilio phlaeas* Linnaeus, 1761 by subsequent designation by Curtis, [1828]. Brit. Entomol. 5: [12](#).
- [NN] *Lycia* Sodoffsky, 1837. Bull. Soc. Nat. Mosc. 10: [81-82](#).
TS: *Papilio phlaeas* Linnaeus, 1761 through Article 67.8 Code ICZN (*Lycia* is a replacement name for *Lycaena* Fabricius, 1807).
- [JS] *Rumicia* Tutt, 1906. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 18(5): [131](#).
TS: *Papilio phlaeas* Linnaeus, 1761 by original designation.

Subgenus

Helleia Verity, 1943

[ORIG] *Lycaena (Helleia)* Verity, 1943. Farfalle diurne Italia 2: [20](#), [48](#).

TS: *Papilio helle* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775 by original designation.

Lycaena helle ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)

[ORIG] *Papilio helle* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775. Ankündigung syst. Werkes Schmett. Wienergegend: [181](#).

TL: Vienna area (Austria).

[JS] *Papilio amphidamas* Esper, [1781]. Schmett. Abb. Nat.1(2): [46-48](#), [pl. 58, fig. 4](#).

TL: Braunschweig (Lower Saxony, Germany).

[JH] *Papilio xanthe* Lang, 1789. Verz. Schmett. Gegend. Ausburg (ed. 2): [52](#).

TL: Leipzig (Saxony, Germany) ; *nec* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775: [181](#).

[JS] *Polyommatus amphidamas* var. *lapponica* Backhaus, 1876. Entomol. Monatsbl. 1: [40](#).

TL: Lapland (N Scandinavia).

[JS] *Chrysophanus amphidamas marchica* Hannemann, 1928. Int. Entomol. Z. 22(22): 210.

TL: Strausberg (Brandenburg, Germany).

[JH] *Heodes amphidamas* ssp. *pyrenaica* Deslandes, 1930. Bull. Soc. entomol. Fr. 15: [243](#).

TL: Porté (Pyrénées-Orientales, S France) ; *nec Lycaena orbitulus* var. *pyrenaica* Boisduval, 1840. Gen. Ind. Meth. Eur. Lepid.: [11](#).

[NN] *Lycaena amphidamas deslandesi* Hemming, 1932. Proc. R. entomol. Soc. Lond.7: [29](#).

Replacement name for *Heodes amphidamas pyrenaica* Deslandes, 1930.

[JS] *Lycaena (Heodes) amphidamas leonia* Beuret, 1936. Lambillionia 36: 272-276.

TL: Tramelan (Berner Jura, Switzerland).

[JS] *Lycaena helle arvernica* Bernardi & de Lesse, 1952. Rev. fr. Lépid. 13(13-14): 203, 211, fig.

TL: Super-Besse, Vallée de Chaudefour (Puy-de-Dôme dep., France).

[JS] *Lycaena (Helleia) helle* ssp. *hellesimilis* Beuret, 1952. Mitt. Entomol. Ges. Basel 2(8): [101-102](#).

TL: Meggen (Lucerne, Switzerland).

[JS] *Lycaena helle magdalenae* Guérin, 1959. Alexanor1(3): 88.

TL: Monts de la Madeleine (Loire dep., France).

[JS] *Lycaena helle* ssp. *perrettei* Weiss, 1977. Linn. Belg.6(10): [254-256, fig.](#)

TL: Gérardmer (Vosges, France).

[JS] *Lycaena helle* ssp. *eneli* Betti, 1977. Alexanor10(2): 92, fig.

TL: Lac de Remoray (Doubs, France).

[JS] *Lycaena helle* ssp. *arduinnae* Meyer, 1980. Linn. Belg.8(3): 131-133, fig.

TL: Hoffelt, Hachiville (Luxembourg).

[JS] *Lycaena helle* ssp. *shchurovi* Gorbunov, 2001. Butt. Russia: [110](#).

TL: Lago-Naki plateau, near the Belorechensky pass (NW Caucasus, Krasnodar Krai, S Russian Federation).

Subgenus

Thersamonia Verity, 1919

[ORIG] *Thersamonia* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(2): [28](#).

TS: *Papilio thersamon* Esper, 1784 by original designation.

Lycaena thetis Klug, 1834

[ORIG] *Lycaena thetis* Klug, 1834. Symb. Phys., Ins. 4: [\[41\]](#), [pl. 40, fig. 17-18](#).

TL: Syria.

[JS] *Thersamonia thetis* ssp. *hephestos* Dils & Poorten, 1982. Phegea 13(4): [109-112, fig. 1-2](#).

TL: Taygetos (S Greece).

Lycaena thersamon (Esper, [1784])

[ORIG] *Papilio thersamon* Esper, [1784]. Schmett. Abb. Nat. 1(2): [176-177, pl. 89 \(cont. 39\), fig. 6](#).

TL: Volgograd (Russian Federation).

[ORIG] *Papilio xanthe* Hübner, [1800]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 69, fig. 347-348](#), [1806]: [53](#).

TL: Volgograd (Russian Federation).

Lycaena phoebus (Blachier, 1905)

[ORIG] *Chrysophanus phoebus* Blachier, 1905. Bull. Soc. entomol. Fr. 1905(13): [212](#).

TL: Morocco.

Subgenus

Thersamolycaena Verity, 1957

[NN] *Thersamonia* (*Thersamolycaena*) Verity, 1957. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 69(10): 225.

TS: *Papilio dispar* Haworth, 1802 by original designation ; replacement name for *Disparia* Verity, 1943.

[JH] *Thersamonia* (*Disparia*) Verity, 1943. Farfalle diurne Ital. 2: 21, 58.

TS: *Papilio dispar* Haworth, 1802 by original designation ; *nec* Nagano, 1916.

[JS] *Lycaena* (*Rapsidia*) Sibatani, 1974. Austral. J. Entomol. 13(2): [109](#).

TS: *Papilio dispar* Haworth, 1802 by original designation.

Lycaena dispar ([Haworth], 1802)

[ORIG] *Papilio dispar* [Haworth], 1802. Prodrromus Lepid. Brit.: [3](#).

TL: England.

[JH] *Papilio hippothoe* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775. Ank. syst. Werkes Schmett. Wienerg.: [181](#).

TL: Austria ; *nec* *Papilio hippothoe* Linnaeus, 1761. Fauna Suec. (ed. 2): [274](#).

[NN] *Papilio rutilus* Werneburg, 1864. Beitr. Schmetterlingsk. 1: [390-391](#).

Replacement name for *Papilio hippothoe* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775.

[JS] *Chrysophanus dispar* var. *festivus* Krulikovsky, 1910. Rev. russe entomol.9: [300](#).

TL: Vyatka (Russian Federation)

- [JS] *Chrysophanus dispar* f. *continentalis* Courvoisier, 1912. Int. entomol. Z. 6(10): [65](#).
TL: Manche (NW France).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus dispar* var. *burdigalensis* Lucas, 1913. Int. entomol. Z. 6(40): [282](#).
TL: Bordeaux area (SW France).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus dispar* var. *batavus* Oberthür, 1923. Ét. lépid. comp. 21(2): 71-75, [pl. 570, fig. 4914, 4915](#).
TL: Friesland (Netherlands).
- [JS] *Thersamonia (Disparia) dispar* race *centralitaliae* Verity, 1943. Farfalle diurne Ital. 2: 61-62, fig. 53-58.
TL: Fosso dell'Abate a Viareggio (Lucca prov., Italy).
- [JS] *Lycaena (Heodes) dispar* ssp. *carueli* Le Moulton, 1945. Misc. Entomol.42(4): 55.
TL: N France.
- [JS] *Lycaena (Heodes) dispar* ssp. *verityi* Le Moulton, 1945. Misc. Entomol.42(4): 57.
TL: Italy, France.
- [JS] *Heodes dispar* ssp. *ramaini* Le Moulton, [1946]. Novit. Entomol. 11-12(1-4): 141.
TL: Ural Mountains (Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Lycaena dispar* ssp. *hungarica* Szabó, 1956. Folia Entomol. Hung. 9(13): [300-302](#).
TL: Kamaraerdő (Hungary).
- [JS] *Lycaena dispar* ssp. *gronieri* Bernardi, 1963. Alexanor3(2): 53.
TL: Aisne (Hauts-de-France, N France).

Subgenus

Paleochrysophanus Verity, 1943

- [ORIG] *Paleochrysophanus* Verity, 1943. Farfalle diurne Ital. 2: 23, 64.
TS: *Papilio hippothoe* Linnaeus, 1761 by original designation.
- [ND] *Paleochrysophanus* Verity, 1934. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 46(5, suppl.): [13, note](#).
TS: *Papilio hippothoe* Linnaeus, 1761 by original designation ; invalid because there is no generic diagnosis.

Lycaena hippothoe (Linnaeus, 1761)

- [ORIG] *Papilio hippothoe* Linnaeus, 1761. Fauna Suecica(Ed. 2): [274](#).
TL: S Sweden.
- [JS] *Papilio chryseis* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775. Ank. syst. Werkes Schmett. Wienerg.: [181](#).
TL: Austria.
- [JH] *Papilio euridice* Rottentburg, 1775. Naturforscher6: [28-29](#).
TL: Austria ; *nec* Johannson, 1763. Centuria Ins. Rar.: [23](#).
- [JS] *Papilio xenophon* Loche, 1801. Mém. Acad. Sci. Turin 6(2): [149-150, pl.8, n.10](#).
TL: Piedmont (NW Italy).
- [JH] *Papilio euridice* Esper, [1804].Schmett. Abb. Nat. Suppl. 1(1): [120, pl. 116, fig. 6-7](#).
nec Johannson, 1763. Centuria Ins. Rar.: [23](#).
- [JS] *Papilio eurydame* Hoffmannsegg, 1806. Mag. f. Insektenk.5: [178](#).
TL: Geneva (Switzerland).

- [JS] *Papilio eurybia* Ochsenheimer, 1808. Schmett. Europa1(2): [81-82](#).
TL: S Switzerland ; Piedmont (NW Italy).
- [JS] [*Polyommatus chryseis*] var. *stiberi* Gerhard, [1852]. Versuch Mon. europ. Schmett.(9): [19](#), [pl. 35, f. 1a-b](#).
TL: Lapland (N Scandinavia).
- [JS] *Polyommatus hippothoe* var. *italica* Calberla, 1887. Corr.-Bl. Entomol. Ver. Iris1(1)(4): [126](#).
TL: Gran Sasso (Abruzzo, C Italy).
- [JS] *Polyommatus hippothoe* var. *groningana* Ter Haar, 1900. Tijdschr. Entomol. 43(3-4): [242](#).
TL: Groningen (Netherlands).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus hippothoe* ssp. *cisalpina* Fruhstorfer, 1909. Int. entomol. Z.3(21): [120](#).
TL: Val Maggia, Fusio (Ticino, Switzerland).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus hippothoe* f. *valderiana* Turati & Verity, 1911. Bull. Soc. entomol. Ital.42: [243-244](#).
TL: Valdieri (Piedmont, NW Italy).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus hippothoe mirus* Verity, 1913. J. Linn. Soc. (Zool.) 32(215): [188](#), [191](#).
TL: Pyrenees (France, Spain).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus hippothoe* var. *stieberioides* Ebert, 1926. Dt. entomol. Z. Iris 40: [35](#).
TL: Oberstdorf (S Bavaria, Germany).
- [JS] *Palaeochrysophanus hippothoe* race *paraerydice* Verity, 1943. Farfalle diurn. Ital. 2: 69.
TL: Val Susa, Bardonecchia (Italy).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus hippothoe* ssp. *parrai* Agenjo, 1944. Eos 20(1-2): [78-79, pl. 2, f. 4-6](#).
TL: Laguna de Camero (La Rioja, N Spain).
- [JS] *Palaeochrysophanus hippothoe* ssp. *engadiniana* Beuret, 1953. Mitt. entomol. Ges. Basel (n.f.)3(1): [6-7](#).
TL: Grisons, Engadine (Switzerland).
- [JS] *Palaeochrysophanus hippothoe* ssp. *bernardii* Beuret, 1955. Mitt. entomol. Ges. Basel (n.f.)5(7): [113-114](#).
TL: Cévennes (France).
- [JS] *Lycaena hippothoe* ssp. *sumadiensis* Szabó, 1956. Folia Entomol. Hung. 9(13): [304](#).
TL: Kaposvár (Hungary).
- [JS] *Lycaena (Palaeochrysophanus) hippothoe* ssp. *curti* Fernández Vidal, 1992. Guia Marip. diurn. Galicia: 94.
TL: Galicia (NW Spain).

***Lycaena candens* (Herrich-Schäffer, [1844])**

- [ORIG] *Polyommatus candens* Herrich-Schäffer, [1844]. Syst. Bearb. Schmett. Eur. 1(7) : [pl. 49, fig. 229-231](#) ; [1845] 1(10): [133](#).
TL: Turkey.
- [JS] *Chrysophanus hippothoe* ssp. *leonhardi* Fruhstorfer, 1917. Entomol. Rundsch.34(4): [16](#).
TL: Bulgaria.
- [JH] *Palaeochrysophanus candens* ssp. *pfeifferi* Beuret, 1952. Mitt. entomol. Ges. Basel(n.f.) 2(7): [59-60](#).
TL: Achalzich (Samtskhe-Javakheti, Georgia).

Subgenus

Heodes Dalman, 1816

- [ORIG] *Zephyrus (Heodes)* Dalman, 1816. K. svenska Vetensk.-Akad. Handl.(1b) 1816: [63](#).
TS: *Papilio virgaureae* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation by Crotch, 1872. Cist. Entomol. 1(4): [71](#).
- [JS] *Chysoptera* Zincken, 1817. Allg.-Lit. Ztg Halle 3(218): [75](#).
TS: *Papilio virgaureae* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation by Tutt, 1906. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 18(5): [131](#).
- [ISS] *Chrysoptera* Tutt, 1906. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 18(5): [131](#).
Incorrect subsequent spelling for *Chysoptera* Zincken, 1817.
- [JS] *Loweia* Tutt, 1906. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 18(5): [131](#).
TS: *Papilio dorilis* Hüfnagel, 1766 by original designation.
- [JS] *Palaeoloweia* Verity, 1934. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 46(5, suppl.): [13](#), [note](#).
TS: *Papilio tityrus* Poda, 1761 by original designation.
- [JS] *Heodes (Alciphronia)* Koçak, 1992. Misc. Pap., CESA (16): [2](#).
TS: *Papilio alciphron* Rottemburg, 1775 by original designation.

Lycaena ottomanus (Lefebvre, [1830])

- [ORIG] *Polyommatus ottomanus* Lefebvre, 1831. Mag. Zool. 1(2): [19\[1+2\]](#), [pl. 46](#), [fig. 3a-b](#).
TL: Balıkesir (W Turkey).
- [JH] *Lycaena legeri* Freyer, 1830. Beitr. eur. Schmett.3(23): [125-126](#), [pl. 133](#), [fig. 1](#).
TL: Istanbul (Turkey).

Lycaena bleusei (Oberthür, 1884)

- [ORIG] *Polyommatus xanthe* f.(var.) *bleusei* Oberthür, 1884. Étud. Entomol. 8: [15 \(nota\)](#), [\[52\]](#).
TL: El Pardo (Madrid, C Spain).

Lycaena virgaureae (Linnaeus, 1758)

- [ORIG] *Papilio virgaureae* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [484](#).
TL: Sweden.
- [JS] *Polyommatus virgaureae* var. *montana* Meyer-Dür, 1852. Verz. Schmett. Schweiz 1: [53](#).
TL: Glacier du Rhône (Valais, Switzerland).
- [JS] *Lycaena oranula* Freyer, 1845. Neuere Beitr. Schmett. 5(76): [120-121](#), pl. 455, fig. 1-2.
TL: Lapland (N Scandinavia).
- [JS] *Polyommatus miegii* Vogel, 1857. Allg. Dt. naturhist. Ztg. 3: [201-206](#), [pl. 6](#), [fig. 1-4](#).
TL: Sierra de Guadarrama, Escorial (C Spain).
- [JS] *Polyommatus virgaureae zermattensis* Fallou, 1865. Ann. Soc. Entomol. Fr. (4)5: [101-102](#), [pl. 2](#), [fig. 3](#).
TL: Zermatt (Valais, Switzerland).
- [JS] *Polyommatus virgaureae* var. *apennina* Calberla, 1888. Corr.-Bl. Entomol. Ver. Iris 1(1)(4): [125](#).
TL: Gran Sasso, Boscolungo (C Italy).
- [JS] *Polyommatus virgaureae* var. *aureomicans* Heyne, 1897. Soc. Entomol.12(2): [9](#).
TL: Taurus, Mersin (S Turkey).

- [JS] *Chrysophanus virgaureae* var. *armeniaca* Bang-Haas, 1906. Dt. entomol. Z. Iris 19(3): [128-129](#).
TL: Tschorum (Armenia).
- [JH] *Chrysophanus virgaureae* var. *caucasica* Jachontov, 1908. Rev. Russe Entomol. 8: [291](#).
TL: N Caucasus (Russian Federation) ; nec *Lycaena corydon* var. *caucasica* Lederer, 1870.
- [JS] *Crysophanus* [sic] *virgaureae* ssp. *athanagild* Fruhstorfer, 1908. Int. entomol. Z. 2(29): [194](#).
TL: Grisons, Engadine (Switzerland).
- [JS] *Chryhsophanus* [sic] *virgaureae* ssp. *juvara* Fruhstorfer, 1908. Int. entomol. Z. 2(29): [195](#).
TL: Passau (Bavaria, S Germany).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus virgaureae* ssp. *osthelderi* Fruhstorfer, 1909. Int. entomol. Z. 3(20): [113](#).
TL: Fusio (Ticino, Switzerland) ; Formazza, Tosafall (Piedmont, NW Italy).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus virgaureae* ssp. *alexandrae* Fruhstorfer, 1909. Int. entomol. Z. 3(21): [120](#).
TL: Turgojak (Ural, Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus virgaureae* ssp. *pelusioti* Fruhstorfer, 1910. Entomol. Z. 24(26): [144](#).
TL: Cogne (N Italy).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus virgaureae* race *inalpinus* Verity, 1913. J. linn. Soc. (Zool.) 32(215): [187](#).
TL: Valdieri (Piedmont, NW Italy).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus virgaureae* ssp. *chrysorhoas* Fruhstorfer, 1917. Dt. entomol. Z. Iris 31(1-2): [33](#).
TL: Homburg (Germany).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus virgaureae* ssp. *cissites* Fruhstorfer, 1917. Dt. entomol. Z. Iris 31(1-2): [34](#).
TL: Gadmental (Bern, Switzerland).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus virgaureae* ssp. *theages* Fruhstorfer, 1917. Dt. entomol. Z. Iris 31(1-2): [40](#).
TL: Le Prese et Brusio, Poschlovtal (Grisons, Switzerland).
- [JS] *Lycaena virgaureae* ssp. *vera* Hemming & Graves, 1928. The Entomologist 61: 87.
TL: Haute-Loire dep. (France).
- [JS] *Lycaena virgaureae* ssp. *pyrenaeicola* Hemming & Graves, 1928. The Entomologist 61: 104.
TL: Pyrénées orientales dep. (France).
- [JS] *Lycaena virgaureae* ssp. *balcanicola* Hemming & Graves, 1928. The Entomologist 61: 106.
TL: Kostenetz (S Bulgaria).
- [JS] *Heodes virgaureae* race *gravesica* Verity, 1929. Bull. Soc. entomol. Fr. 1929(7): [129](#).
TL: Aigoual (Lozère dep., France).
- [JS] *Heodes virgaureae* race *mediomontana* Verity, 1929. Bull. Soc. entomol. Fr. 1929(7): [131](#).
TL: Col de Sestrières (Piedmont, NW Italy) ; Montgenèvre (Hautes-Alpes dep., SE France).
- [JS] *Heodes virgaureae* race *pyrenemontana* Verity, 1929. Bull. Soc. entomol. Fr. 1929(7): [131](#).
TL: Gèdre (Hautes-Pyrénées dep., France).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus virgaureae* ssp. *delicata* Higgins, 1930. The Entomologist 63(804): 99.
TL: Piedmont (NW Italy).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus virgaureae* ssp. *rhenana* Heydemann, 1943. Dt. entomol. Z. Iris 55: 99.
TL: Germany.
- [JS] *Lycaena virgaureae* ssp. *pyronitens* Szabó, 1956. Folia entomol. Hung. 9(13): [299](#), [340](#).
TL: Hungary.

- [JS] *Lycaena (Heodes) virgaureae denizae* Eckweiler & Rose, 1993. Nachr. Entomol. Ver. Apollo NF 13(3a): [356, pl. 1, f. 1-8](#).
TL: Isparta, Eğirdir, Aksu, Dedegöl Dağ (Turkey).
- [NN] *Lycaena virgaureae* nom. nov. *mikaeli* Tsvetkov, 2010. Caucasian Entomol. Bull.6(1): [99](#).
Replacement name for *Chrysophanus virgaureae caucasica* Jachontov, 1908.

Lycaena tityrus (Poda, 1761)

- [ORIG] *Papilio tityrus* Poda, 1761. Ins. Mus. Graec.: [77](#).
TL: Graz area (Austria).
- [JS] *Papilio acrion* Brünnich, 1763. In: Pontoppidan, Danske Atlas 1: [685-686, pl. 30, fig. \[1\]](#).
TL: Denmark.
- [JS] *Papilio dorilis* Hufnagel, 1766. Berlin. Mag. 2(1): [68-69](#).
TL: Berlin (Germany).
- [JS] *Papilio phocas* Rottemburg, 1775. Der Naturforscher 6: [29](#).
TL: Germany.
- [JS] *Papilio xanthe* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775. Ank. syst. Werkes Schmett. Wienerg.: [181](#).
TL: Vienna area (Austria).
- [JH] *Papilio circe* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775. Ank. syst. Werkes Schmett. Wienerg.: [181](#).
TL: Vienna area (Austria) ; *nec Papilio circe* Fabricius, 1775. Syst. entomol.: [495](#).
- [JH] *Papilio rubi* Geoffroy, 1785. Entomol. Paris 2: [245](#).
TL: Paris (France) ; *nec Papilio rubi* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [483](#).
- [JS] *Papilio garbus* Fabricius, 1787. Mantissa Insect. 2: [81](#).
TL: Austria.
- [JS] *Polyommatus myopa* Latreille, 1805. Hist. nat. Crust. Ins. 14: [121](#).
TL: France, Germany.
- [JS] *Polyommatus circe* var. *subalpina* Speyer, 1851. Entomol. Ztg.12(11): [339](#).
TL: Patscher Kofel (Tirol, Austria).
- [JS] *Polyommatus xanthe* var. *montana* Meyer-Dür, 1852. Verz. Schmett. Schweiz1: [60](#).
TL: Gotthard Pass (Ticino, Switzerland).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus dorilis* var. *locarnensis* Tutt, 1903. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 15(9): [224](#).
TL: Locarno (Ticino, Switzerland).
- [JS] *Loweia dorilis* race *italorum* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(2): [29](#).
TL: Italy.
- [JS] *Chrysophanus dorilis* ssp. *reverdini* Stauder, 1921. Dt. entomol. Z. Iris 35: [30](#).
TL: Faito, Aspromonte (S Italy).
- [JS] *Palaeoloweia tityrus* race *pallidepicta* Verity, 1934. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 46(suppl.): [16](#).
TL: Mont Ventoux (Vaucluse dep., S France).
- [JS] *Palaeoloweia tityrus* race *praebileusei* Verity, 1934. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 46(suppl.): [17](#).
TL: Puerto de Pajares (Asturias, NW Spain).
- [JS] *Heodes (Chrysophanus) tityrus* race *catherinei* Verity, 1948. Var. géogr. saison. pap. diurn. Fr.: [58](#).
TL: Val de Héas (Hautes-Pyrénées dep., S France).

- [JS] *Heodes (Chrysophanus) tityrus* race *oceanitis* Verity, 1948. Var. géogr. saison. pap. diurn. Fr.: [58](#).
TL: Marsas, St. Côme (Gironde dep.), Puybelliard, Olonne (Vendée dep.) (W France).
- [JS] *Heodes (Chrysophanus) tityrus* race *mixtalpina* Verity, 1948. Var. géogr. saison. pap. diurn. Fr.: [60](#).
TL: Vallée du Boréon (Alpes-Maritimes dep., SE France).
- [JS] *Lycaena (Heodes) tityrus argentifex* Bálint, 1990. Janus Pannonius Múz. Évkönyve 34: [54-59, fig. 1-4](#).
TL: Békási-szoros, Kupás-p. (Romania).

***Lycaena alciphron* (Rottemburg, 1775)**

- [ORIG] *Papilio alciphron* Rottemburg, 1775. Naturforscher 6: [10-11](#).
TL: Berlin area (E Germany).
- [JH] *Papilio virgaeaureae* Hufnagel, 1766. Berlin. Mag. 2(1): [80-81](#).
TL: Berlin area (E Germany) ; nec *Papilio virgaeaureae* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [484](#).
- [JS] *Papilio lampetie* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775. Ank. syst. Werkes Schmett. Wienerg.: [322](#).
TL: Vienna area (Austria).
- [JS] *Papilio gordius* Sulzer, 1776. Abg. Gesch. Ins. 1: [146](#).
TL: Bünden (Grisons, Switzerland).
- [JH] *Papilio hippothoe* Esper, [1777]. Schmett. Abb. Nat. 1(1): [342-343](#) [1779], [pl. 35, fig. 5](#) [1777].
TL: Germany ; nec *Papilio hippothoe* Linnaeus, 1761. Fauna Suec. (ed. 2): [274](#).
- [JS] *Papilio hieze* Fabricius, 1787. Mantissa Insect. 2: [80](#).
TL: Austria.
- [JH] *Papilio helle* Borkhausen, 1788. Naturg. eur. Schmett. 1: [146-147](#).
TL: Germany ; nec *Papilio helle* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775. Ank. syst. Werkes Schmett. Wienerg.: [181](#).
- [JS] *Papilio columbanus* Prunner, 1798. Lepid. Pedemont.: [76](#).
TL: Piedmont (NW Italy).
- [JS] *Polyommatus alciphron intermedia* Stefanelli, 1874. Bull. Soc. entomol. Ital. 6: [85](#).
TL: Tuscany (Italy).
- [JS] *Polyommatus alciphron* var. *melibaeus* Staudinger, 1878. Horae Soc. Entomol. Ross. 14(2-3): [231-232](#).
TL: Amasya (N Turkey).
- [JS] *Polyommatus cupreus* Cosmovici, 1892. Naturaliste 14(136): [255](#).
TL: Neamț (Romania).
- [JS] *Chrysophanes gordius* var. *granadensis* Ribbe, 1905. Soc. entomol. 20(18): [138](#).
TL: Andalusia (S Spain).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus alciphron* ssp. *isokrates* Fruhstorfer, 1909. Int. Entomol. Z. 3(21): [120](#).
TL: Simplon, Iselle (Switzerland) ; Val de Cogne (Aoste, NW Italy).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus alciphron* ssp. *romanorum* Fruhstorfer, 1909. Int. Entomol. Z. 3(21): [120](#).
TL: Rome (C Italy).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus alciphron* ssp. *gaudeolus* Fruhstorfer, 1909. Int. Entomol. Z. 3(21): [120](#).
TL: Zermatt (Valais, Switzerland) ; Lana (South Tyrol, SE Italy).
- [JS] *Polyommatus gordius diniensis* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. Lépid. comp. 4: [114](#), [667](#), [pl. 38, fig. 245](#).
TL: Digne (Alpes-de-Haute-Provence dep., SE France).

- [JS] *Polyommatus gordius rondoui* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. Lépid. comp. 4: [114](#), [667](#), [pl. 38, fig. 246](#).
TL: Gèdre (Hautes-Pyrénées dep., S France).
- [JS] *Polyommatus gordius nevadensis* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. Lépid. comp. 4: [114](#), [667](#), [pl. 38, fig. 248](#).
TL: Sierra Nevada (Andalusia, S Spain).
- [JS] *Polyommatus gordius bellieri* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. Lépid. comp. 4: [114](#), [667](#), [pl. 38, fig. 249-250](#).
TL: Madonie (Sicily, S Italy).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus alciphron* ssp. *aetnea* Turati, 1911. Soc. Entomol. 25(21): [81-82](#).
TL: Catane, Nicolosi Etnea (Sicily, S Italy).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus alciphron* ssp. *ruehli* Turati, 1911. Soc. Entomol. 25(21): [83](#).
TL: Cerchio (Abruzzo, C Italy).
- [IFS] *Chrysophanus alciphron gordius* s.-race *calabrus* Verity, 1913. Bull. Soc. entomol. ital. 45: [228](#), [pl. 1, fig. 43](#).
TL: Piani di Carmelia, Aspromonte (Calabria, S Italy).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus alciphron* ssp. *chairemon* Fruhstorfer, 1917. Entomol. Rdsch. 34(4): [16-17](#).
TL: Orsowa (Bulgaria) ; Herzegovina (Bosnia and Herzegovina).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus alciphron* ssp. *fruginus* Fruhstorfer, 1917. Entomol. Rdsch. 34(4): [17](#).
TL: Armenia.
- [JS] *Chrysophanus alciphron* ssp. *madytus* Fruhstorfer, 1917. Entomol. Rdsch. 34(4): [17](#).
TL: Petralia (Sicily, S Italy).
- [ND] *Chrysophanus alciphron* ssp. *gallon* Fruhstorfer, 1917. Entomol. Rdsch. 34(4): [17](#).
TL: Digne (Alpes-de-Haute-Provence dep., SE France) ; nomen nudum, not described.
- [JS] *Chrysophanus alciphron* ssp. *veronius* Fruhstorfer, 1917. Entomol. Rdsch. 34(4): [17](#).
TL: Gèdre (Hautes-Pyrénées dep., S France).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus alciphron* ssp. *epidelion* Fruhstorfer, 1917. Entomol. Rdsch. 34(4): [17-18](#).
TL: Alpes-Maritimes (SE France).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus alciphron* ssp. *deinaretton* Fruhstorfer, 1917. Entomol. Rdsch. 34(4): [18](#).
TL: Gran Sasso, Sibillini Mountains (C Italy).
- [JS] *Loweia alciphron* race *mirabilis* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(2): [28-29](#).
TL: Monte Senario, Vaglia (Tuscany, Italy).
- [JS] *Loweia alciphron* race *insignis* de Sagarra, 1924. Butll. Inst. Catal. Hist. nat. (2)4(9): [201](#).
TL: Albarracin (Aragón, Spain).
- [JS] *Loweia alciphron* race *paupercula* de Sagarra, 1924. Butll. Inst. Catal. Hist. nat. (2)4(9): [201-202](#).
TL: Puerto de Orihuela del Tremedal (Aragón, Spain).
- [JH] *Chrysophanus alciphron violacea* Pionneau, 1926. Échange 42(424): 7.
TL: Gironde (E France) ; *nec Polyommatus chryseis violacea* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. Lépid. comp. 4: [130](#).
- [JS] *Loweia alciphron* race *ultragordius* Verity, 1926. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 38(7/8): [105](#).
TL: Oulx (Piedmont, NW Italy).
- [NN] *Heodes (Chrysophanus) alciphron* race *oceani* Verity, 1943. Farfalle diurn. Ital. 2: 43.
Replacement name for *Chrysophanus alciphron violacea* Pionneau, 1922.
- [JS] *Heodes (Chrysophanus) alciphron* race *citragordius* Verity, 1943. Farfalle diurn. Ital. 2: 45-46.
TL: Turbigo (Lombardy, NW Italy).

- [JS] *Heodes (Chrysophanus) alciphron* race *minutepunctata* Verity, 1948. Var. géogr. saison. pap. diurn. Fr.: [62-63](#).
TL: Champ de tir de Nîmes (Gard dep., S France).
- [JS] *Heodes (Chrysophanus) alciphron* ssp. *rhaetica* Beuret, 1952. Mitt. entomol. Ges. Basel (NF) 2: [86](#).
TL: Ardez, Tarasp (Graubünden, Switzerland).
- [JS] *Lycaena alciphron* ssp. *cumanicus* Szabó, 1956. Folia entomol. Hung. (NS) 9(13): [305](#), [340](#).
TL: Peszér (Hungary).
- [JS] *Heodes alciphron* ssp. *ochsenfeldinus* Betti, 1977. Alexanor 10(2): 91.
TL: Germany.
- [JS] *Lycaena alciphron* ssp. *burgundiae* Bellenger & Descimon, 1977. Alexanor 10(4): 165.
TL: Bourgogne (NE France).
- [JS] *Lycaena alciphron* ssp. *morvandica* Bellenger & Descimon, 1977. Alexanor 10(4): 166.
TL: Morvan (France).
- [JS] *Heodes alciphron* ssp. *boyarensis* Verdugo-Páez, 1984. SHILAP 12(45): [56](#).
TL: Grazalema (Cádiz prov., S Spain).

ESU *L. heracleana* (Blachier, 1908)

- [JS] *Chrysophanus alciphron* var. *heracleana* Blachier, 1908. Ann. Soc. entomol. Fr. 77(2): [217](#).
TL: Atlas Mountains (Morocco).

Subgenus

Lycaena Fabricius, 1807

- [ORIG] *Lycaena* Fabricius, 1807. In: Illiger, Mag. Insektenk. 6: [285-286](#).
TS: *Papilio phlaeas* Linnaeus, 1761 by subsequent designation by Curtis, [1828]. Brit. Entomol. 5: [12](#).
- [NN] *Lycia* Sodoffsky, 1837. Bull. Soc. Nat. Mosc. 10: [81-82](#).
TS: *Papilio phlaeas* Linnaeus, 1761 through Article 67.8 Code ICZN (*Lycia* is a replacement name for *Lycaena* Fabricius, 1807).
- [JS] *Rumicia* Tutt, 1906. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 18(5): [131](#).
TS: *Papilio phlaeas* Linnaeus, 1761 by original designation.

Lycaena phlaeas (Linnaeus, 1761)

- [ORIG] *Papilio phlaeas* Linnaeus, 1761. Fauna Suec. (ed. 2): [285](#).
TL: Västmanland (Sweden).
- [JH] *Papilio virgaureae* Scopoli, 1763. Entomol. Carniol.: [180-181](#).
TL: Slovenia ; *nec* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [484](#).
- [JS] *Papilio timeus* Cramer, [1777]. Uitl. Kap. 2(16): [137](#), [pl. 186](#), [fig. E-F](#).
TL: Izmir (Turkey).
- [JS] *Hesperia eleus* Fabricius, 1798. Suppl. Entomol. Syst.: [430-431](#).
TL: Germany.
- [JS] *Polyommatus turcicus* Gerhard, [1850]. Vers. Monogr. eur. Schmett. (2): [5](#), [pl. 5](#), [fig. 5](#).
TL: Turkey.

- [JS] *Polyommatus xanthe* var. *schmidtii* Gerhard, [1850]. Vers. Monogr. eur. Schmett. (3): [7](#), [pl. 10, fig. 3](#).
TL: Europe.
- [JS] *Polyommatus phlaeas* var. *cuprinus* Peyerimhoff, 1862. Cat. Lepid. Alsace: [13](#).
TL: Hohneck (Vosges, NE France).
- [JS] *Polyommatus phlaeas* var. *transiens* Fuchs, 1899. Jahrb. Nassauisch. Ver. Naturk. 52: [120](#).
TL: Loreley (Rhineland-Palatinate, Germany).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus phlaeas* var. *phlaeoides* Staudinger, 1901. In: Staudinger & Rebel, Cat. Lepid. pal. Fauneng.: [74](#).
TL: Madeira (Portugal).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus phlaeas* f. *polaris* Courvoisier, 1911. Entomol. Z. 24(49): [262](#).
TL: Lapland (N Norway).
- [JS] *Rumicia phlaeas* race *nigrioreleus* Verity, 1920. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 32(1): [5](#).
TL: Tuscany (Italy).
- [JS] *Rumicia phlaeas* race *varieleus* Verity, 1920. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 32(1): [5-7](#).
TL: Valdieri (Cuneo prov., Piedmont, NW Italy).
- [JS] *Rumicia (Chrysophanus) phlaeas* f. *cyrenaica* Turati, 1922. Atti Soc. ital. Sci. nat. Milano 60: [219-220](#).
TL: Uadi Derna (Cyrenaica prov., Libya).
- [JS] *Heodes phlaeas* race *hyperborea* Ford, 1924. Trans. Entomol. Soc. Lond. 1923(5): [739](#), [pl. 54, fig. 6](#).
TL: Arctic Norway.
- [JS] *Heodes phlaeas lusitanica* Bryk, 1940. Arkiv Zool. 32A(22): 20, pl. 6, fig. 37-38.
TL: Portugal.
- [JS] *Lycaena phlaeas* ssp. *hibernica* Goodson, 1948. The Entomologist 81: 177.
TL: Ireland.

Subgenus

Phoenicurusia Verity, 1943

- [ORIG] *Lycaena (Phoenicurusia)* Verity, 1943. Farfalle diurne Italia 2: [21](#).
TS: *Polyommatus phoenicurus* Lederer, 1870 by original designation.
- [JS] *Athamanthia* Zhdanko, 1983. Entomol. Obozr. 62: 161.
TS: *Lycaena athamantis* Eversmann, 1854 by original designation.

Lycaena japhetica Nekrutenko & Effendi, 1983

- [ORIG] *Lycaena japhetica* Nekrutenko & Effendi, 1983. Vestnik. Zool. 1983(4): [12](#).
TL: Dizavarchay river (Absheron distr., Azerbaijan).
- [ORIG] *Lycaena japhetica irghiza* Nekrutenko, 1985. Vestnik. Zool. 1985(4): [31-32, fig.](#)
TL: Irghiz (Aktjubinsk reg., Kazakhstan).

Subfamily

Theclinae Swainson, 1831

- [ORIG] Theclanae Swainson, 1831. Zool. Illustr. (2)2: [\[text pl. 85\]](#).
TG: *Thecla* Fabricius, 1807.

Tribe

Theclini Swainson, 1831

[ORIG] Theclanae Swainson, 1831. Zool. Illustr. (2)2: [\[text pl. 85\]](#).

TG: *Thecla* Fabricius, 1807.

Genus

Thecla Fabricius, 1807

[ORIG] *Thecla* Fabricius, 1807. In: Illiger, Mag. Insektenk. 6: [286](#).

TS: *Papilio betulae* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation by Swainson, 1821. Zool. Illustr. 2: 482.

[JS] *Theclaria* Rafinesque, 1815. Analyse Nat.: [128](#).

TS: *Papilio betulae* Linnaeus, 1758 by monotypy.

[JS] *Zephyrus* Dalman, 1816. K. svenska Vetensk.-Akad. Handl. (1b) 1816: [62](#).

TS: *Papilio betulae* Linnaeus, 1758 by original designation.

[JS] *Aurotis* Dalman, 1816. K. svenska Vetensk.-Akad. Handl. (1b) 1816: [63](#).

TS: *Papilio betulae* Linnaeus, 1758 by monotypy.

[JS] *Ruralis* Tutt, 1906. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 18(5): [130](#).

TS: *Papilio betulae* Linnaeus, 1758 by original designation.

[JS] *Iozephyrus* Wang & Fan, 2002. Butt. Fauna Sinica, Lycaenidae: 30.

TS: *Thecla betulina* Staudinger, 1887 by original designation.

Thecla betulae Fabricius, 1807

[ORIG] *Papilio betulae* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [482](#).

TL: Sweden.

[JS] *Papilio apelles* Villers, 1789. Caroli Linnei Entomol. 2: [536](#).

TL: Lyon (C France).

[JS] *Thecla betulae* var. *spinosae* Gerhard, [1850]. Vers. Monogr. eur. Schmett. (2): [3](#), [pl. 3](#), [fig. 2](#).

TL: Europa.

Genus

Favonius Sibatani & Ito, 1942

[ORIG] *Favonius* Sibatani & Ito, 1942. Tenthredo 3(4): 327.

TS: *Dipsas orientalis* Murray, 1875 by original designation.

[JS] *Quercusia* Verity, 1943. Farfalle diurne Italia 2: 343.

TS: *Papilio quercus* Linnaeus, 1758 by original designation.

Favonius quercus (Linnaeus, 1758)

[ORIG] *Papilio quercus* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [482](#).

TL: England (UK).

[JS] *Papilio epeus* Sulzer, 1776. Gesch. Ins. nach linn. Syst. 1: [145-146](#) ; 2: [pl. 18](#), [fig. 10](#).

TL: Switzerland.

- [JS] *Thecla quercus* var. *bellus* Gerhard, [1850]. Vers. Monogr. eur. Schmett. (2): [4](#), [pl. 4, fig. 2](#).
TL: Europe.
- [JS] *Zephyrus quercus* var. *iberica* Staudinger, 1901. Cat. Lep. Pal. Fauneng. 1: [71](#).
TL: C and S Iberian Peninsula ; Mauretania (Morocco).
- [JS] *Thecla quercus* var. *violacea* Niepelt, 1914. Int. Entomol. Z. 8(26): [144](#).
TL: Magdeburg (Germany).
- [JS] *Bithis quercus* race *interjecta* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(3): [48](#).
TL: Italy.

Genus

Laeosopis Rambur, 1858

- [ORIG] *Laeosopis* Rambur, 1858. Cat. syst. lépid. Andal.: [33](#).
TS: *Papilio roboris* Esper, 1789 by monotypy.
- [JH] *Aurotis* Kirby, 1862. Man. Eur. Butt. : [87](#).
TS: *Papilio roboris* Esper, 1789 by monotypy ; *nec Aurotis* Dalman, 1816. K. svenska Vetensk.-Akad. Handl. (1b) 1816: [63](#).

Laeosopis roboris (Esper, [1793])

- [ORIG] *Papilio roboris* Esper, [1793]. Schmett. Abb. Nat.Suppl. 1(1): [59-60](#), [pl. 103 \(cont. 58\)](#), [fig. 5](#).
TL: Frankfurt (Hesse, Germany).
[very likely error, probably SW Europe]
- [JS] *Papilio evippus* Hübner, 1793. Samml. Ausserl. Vög. Schmett.: [11](#), pl. [56-57](#).
TL: -.
- [JS] *Papilio evippus* Hübner, [1800]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 73, fig. 366-367](#), [1806]: [55-56](#).
TL: Spain.
- [JS] *Laeosopis roboris* var. *lusitanica* Staudinger, 1892. Dt. Entomol. Z. 4(2): [232](#).
TL: Algarve (S Portugal).
- [JS] *Jamides roboris* race *escorialensis* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. Lépid. Comp. 4: [57](#).
TL: El Escorial (C Spain).
- [JS] *Laeosopis roboris* race *demissa* Verity, 1943. Farfalle diurne Italia 2: 342.
TL: Guillaumes (Alpes Maritimes dep., SE France).
- [JS] *Laeosopis roboris magis* Agenjo, 1963. Bol. Serv. Plag. Forest. 6(12): 136.
TL: NW Spain.
- [JS] *Laeosopis roboris mudarra* Agenjo, 1963. Bol. Serv. Plag. Forest. 6(12): 137.
TL: NE Spain.
- [JS] *Laeosopis roboris higginsi* Agenjo, 1963. Bol. Serv. Plag. Forest. 6(12): 138.
TL: Granada (S Spain).
- [JS] *Laeosopis roboris portaensis* Betti, 1977. Alexanor 10(2): 93.
TL: Porté (Pyrénées-Orientales dep., S France).
- [JS] *Laeosopis roboris thiersi* Betti, 1977. Alexanor 10(2): 94.
TL: Lamalou-les-Bains (Hérault dep., S France).

Tribe

Deudorigini Doherty, 1886

[ORIG] Deudoriginae Doherty, 1886. J. asiat. Soc. Bengal. (2) 55(2): [110](#).

TG: *Deudorix* Hewitson, 1863.

Genus

Deudorix Hewitson, 1863

[ORIG] *Deudorix* Hewitson, 1863. Ill. diurn. Lepid. Lycaenidae 1: [16-17](#).

TS: *Dipsas epijarbas* Moore, 1858 by original designation.

[JS] *Virachola* Moore, [1881]. Lepid. Ceylon 1(3): [104](#).

TS: *Deudorix perse* Hewitson, 1863 by original designation.

Deudorix livia (Klug, 1834)

[ORIG] *Lycaena livia* Klug, 1834. Symb. Phys., Ins. 4: [[39-40](#)], [pl. 40, fig. 3-4](#).

TL: Egypt.

Tribe

Tomarini Eliot, 1973

[ORIG] Tomarini Eliot, 1973. Bull. Brit. Mus. (N.H.) Entomol. 28(6): [439](#).

TG: *Tomares* Rambur, [1840].

Genus

Tomares Rambur, [1840]

[ORIG] *Tomares* Rambur, [1840]. Faune entomol. Andal. 2(5): 261.

TS: *Papilio ballus* Fabricius, 1787 by monotypy.

Tomares ballus (Fabricius, 1787)

[ORIG] *Papilio ballus* Fabricius, 1787. Mantissa Ins. 2: [80](#).

TL: Spain.

[JS] *Tomares (Thestor) ballus* ssp. *mareoticus* Graves, 1918. Entomologist 51(660): [97-98](#), [pl. 1, fig. 1-2](#).

TL: Dekehla (Egypt).

[JS] *Thestor ballus cyrenaica* Turati, 1924. Atti Soc. Ital. Sci. Nat. 63: [35-36](#), pl. 1, fig. 14-16.

TL: Berca e Tocra, Benghazi (Libya).

[JS] *T. ballus* race *phychrokoilios* Forbes, 1929. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 41(1): [10](#).

TL: Ronda (S Spain).

[JS] *Thestor ballus* race *catalonica* Sagarra, 1930. Butll. Inst. catal. Hist. nat. (2)10(7): [116](#).

TL: Vallvidrera, Sant Medi (Catalonia, NE Spain).

Tomares mauritanicus (Lucas, 1849)

- [ORIG] *Polyommatus mauritanicus* Lucas, 1849. Explor. Scient. Algérie, Hist. nat. Anim. articul. 3: [360](#), pl. 1, [fig. 9a-c](#).
TL: Béjaïa (Algeria).
- [JS] *Tomares mauretanicus* [sic] ssp. *amelnorum* Tarrier, 1998. Alexanor 20(2): 120, fig. 23-24.
TL: Aït-Baha (Anti-Atlas, Morocco).
- [JS] *Tomares mauritanicus antonius* Brévignon, 1985. Alexanor 13(8): 342, fig.
TL: Col de Zad (Middle-Atlas, Morocco).

Tomares nogelii (Herrich-Schäffer, [1851])

- [ORIG] *Thecla nogelii* Herrich-Schäffer, [1851]. Syst. Bearb. Schmett. Eur. 1: [pl. 110, fig. 529-532](#) ; 6(Nachtrag): [33-34](#) [1852].
TL: Amasia (Turkey).
- [JS] *Thestor nogelii* var. *dobrogensis* Caradja, 1895. Dt. Entomol. Z. 8: [34](#).
TL: Tulcea (Dobruja, Romania).

Tomares callimachus (Eversmann, 1848)

- [ORIG] *Lycaena callimachus* Eversmann, 1848. Bull. Soc. imp. nat. Mosc. 21(3): [208-210](#).
TL: Helenendorf (= Goygol, [Azerbaijan](#)).
- [JS] *Tomares callimachus* ssp. *tauricus* Korb & Yakovlev, 1998. *Lambillionea* 98(1): 141.
TL: Sudak (Crimea).

Tribe

Eumaeini Doubleday, 1847

- [ORIG] Eumaeidae Doubleday, 1847. List Spec. lepid. Ins. Coll. Brit. Mus. (2): [20](#).
TG: *Eumaeus* Hübner, [1819].

Genus

Callophrys Billberg, 1820

- [ORIG] *Callophrys* Billberg, 1820. Enum. Ins. Mus. Billb.: [80](#).
TS: *Papilio rubi* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation by Scudder, 1875. Proc. Am. Acad. Arts Sci. 10(2): [132](#).
- [JH] *Lycus* Hübner, [1819]. Verz. bekannt. Schmett.: [74](#).
TS: *Papilio rubi* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation by Scudder, 1875. Proc. Am. Acad. Arts Sci. 10(2): [210](#) ; *nec* Fabricius, 1787. Mantissa Ins. 1: 163.

Callophrys avis Chapman, 1909

- [ORIG] *Callophrys avis* Chapman, 1909. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 21(6): [130-131](#).
TL: S France.
- [JS] *Callophris* [sic] *avis* f. *semipallida* Barragué, 1954. Bull. Soc. Hist. Nat. Afr. N. 45(3-4): 185.
TL: Algeria.
- [JS] *Callophrys avis* ssp. *barraguei* Dujardin, 1972. Entomops 4(25): 7-8, fig. 1.
TL: Kaddous (Algeria), Ifrane (Morocco).

- [JS] *Callophrys avis* ssp. *lhafii* Tarrier, 2017. Alexanor 28(2): [105-106, fig. 4-5](#).
TL: Ait-Iftene (SW Anti-Atlas, Morocco).
- [JS] *Callophrys rubi* [sic] ssp. *pumilio* Tarrier, 2017. Alexanor 28(2): [108-110, fig. 7](#).
TL: Tizi-Tazouguart (Middle Atlas, Morocco).

Callophrys suaveola (Staudinger, 1881)

- [ORIG] *Thecla rubi* var. *suaveola* Staudinger, 1881. Entomol. Ztg. 42(7-9): [279-280](#).
TL: Lepsy Valley (Kazakhstan).
- [JS] *Callophrys butlerovi* Migranov, 1992. Zool. Ž.71(5): 135-140, fig.
TL: S Ural (Russian Federation).

Callophrys rubi (Linnaeus, 1758)

- [ORIG] *Papilio rubi* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [483](#).
TL: Sweden.
- [JS] *Papilio caecus* Geoffroy, 1785. Entomol. Paris. 2: [245-246](#).
TL: Paris (France).
- [JS] *Thecla rubi* var. *borealis* Krulikovskiy, 1890. Bull. Soc. imp. Nat. Moscou (n.s.)4(2): [217-218](#).
TL: Kazan (Tatarstan, Russia Federation).
- [JS] *Thecla rubi* var. *polaris* Krulikovskiy, 1893. Soc. Entomol. 7(21): [164](#).
TL: Vyatka Governorate (Volga-Vyatka, Russia Federation).
- [JS] *Callophrys rubi* var. *fervida* Staudinger, 1901. Cat. Lep. Pal. Fauneng. 1: [70](#).
TL: S Iberian Peninsula ; Mauretania ; ...
- [JS] *Callophrys rubi* var. *intermedia* Tutt, [1907]. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 9: 91.
TL: S Europe.
- [JS] *Callophrys rubi* race *virgatus* Verity, 1913. J. linn. Soc. (Zool.) 32(215): [187](#).
TL: C and S Europe (Germany ?).
- [JS] *Callophrys rubi* var. *foulquieri* Revertegat, 1914. Bull. Soc. Hist. Nat. Afr. N. 5(6): [154-155, fig. 2-4](#).
TL: Bône (= Annaba, NE Algeria).
- [JS] *Callophrys rubi* var. *leucosticta* Stauder, 1923. Z. Wiss. Ins.-Biol. 18(3-4): [66](#).
TL: NE Italy.

Callophrys chalybeitincta Sovinsky, 1905

- [ORIG] *Callophrys rubi* var. *chalybeitincta* Sovinsky, 1905. Rev. Russ. Entomol. 5(3-4): [109](#).
TL: Derbent (Daghestan, Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Callophrys rubi* var. *caerulescens* Bang-Haas, 1912. Dt. Entomol. Z. 26(2): [106](#).
TL: Elizavetpol (Azerbaijan).
- [JS] *Callophrys rubi* var. *schamyl* Sheldon, 1914. Entomologist 47(617): [272](#).
TL: Novorossiysk (South Caucasus, Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Callophrys chalybeitincta nigra* Stradomsky, 2005. Cauc. Entomol. Bull. 1(1): [85-86, fig. 1](#).
TL: Rostov-on-Don, Kumzhensky forest (North Caucasus, Russian Federation).

Genus

Neolycaena Nicéville, 1890

[ORIG] *Neolycaena* Nicéville, 1890. Butt. India Burmah Ceylon 3: [64-65](#).

TS: *Lycaena sinensis* Alphéraky, 1881 by original designation.

[JS] *Rhymnaria* Zhdanko, 1983. Entomol. Obozr. 62(1): 150.

TS: *Lycaena rhymnus* Evesmann, 1832 by original designation.

Neolycaena rhymnus (Eversmann, 1832)

[ORIG] *Lycaena rhymnus* Eversmann, 1832. Nouv. Mém. Soc. imp. nat. Moscou 2: [350](#), [pl. 19, fig. 1-2](#).

TL: S Ural (Kazakhstan ; Russian Federation).

Genus

Satyrium Scudder, 1876

[ORIG] *Satyrium* Scudder, 1876. Bull. Buff. Soc. nat. Sci. 3(15): [106](#).

TS: *Lycaena fuliginosa* Edwards, 1861 by original designation.

[JH] *Argus* Gerhard, [1850]. Versuch Monogr. eur. Schmett. (8): [4](#).

TS: *Lycaena ledereri* Boisduval, 1848 by monotypy ; *nec Argus* Bohadsch, 1761.

[JS] *Callipsyche* Scudder, 1876. Bull. Buffalo Soc. Nat. Sci. 3: [106-107](#).

TS: *Thecla behrii* Edwards, 1870 by original designation.

[JS] *Fixsenia* Tutt, [1907]. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 9: [142](#).

TS: *Thecla herzi* Fixsen, 1887 by original designation.

[JH] *Leechia* Tutt, [1907]. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 9: [142](#).

TS: *Thecla thalia* Leech, 1893 by original designation ; *nec Leechia* South, 1901 ; replaced by *Strymonidia* Tutt, [1908].

[JH] *Strymon* Hübner, [1819] sensus Tutt, [1907]. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 9: [142](#), [192-195](#).

TS: *Papilio pruni* Linnaeus, 1758 by original designation.

[JH] *Felderia* Tutt, [1907]. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 9: [142](#).

TS: *Thecla w-album eximia* Fixsen, 1887 by original designation ; *nec Felderia* Walsingham, 1887.

[JH] *Edwardsia* Tutt, [1907]. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 9: [142](#), [144-145](#).

TS: *Papilio w-album* Knoch, 1782 by original designation ; *nec Edwardsia* Costa, 1838 ; replaced by *Chattendenia* Tutt, [1908].

[JH] *Kuglia* Tutt, [1907]. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 9: [142](#).

TS: *Papilio spini* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775 by original designation ; *nec Klugia* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1863.

[JH] *Kollaria* Tutt, [1907]. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 9: [142](#).

TS: *Thecla sassanides* Kollar, 1850 by original designation ; *nec Kollaria* Pictet, 1841.

[JH] *Erschoffia* Tutt, [1907]. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 9: [142](#).

TS: *Thecla lunulata* Erschoff, 1874 by original designation ; *nec Erschoffia* Swinhoe, 1900.

[JH] *Bakeria* Tutt, [1907]. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 9: [142](#).

TS: *Lycaena ledereri* Boisduval, 1848 by original designation ; *nec Bakeria* Kieffer, 1905.

[JS] *Nordmannia* Tutt, [1907]. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 9: [142-143](#).

TS: *Lycaena myrtale* Klug, 1834 by original designation.

- [NN] *Strymonidia* Tutt, [1908]. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 9: [483](#).
Replacement name for *Leechia* Tutt, [1907].
- [NN] *Chattendenia* Tutt, [1908]. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 9: [483](#).
Replacement name for *Edwardsia* Tutt, [1907].
- [NN] *Tuttiolia* Strand, 1910. Entomol. Rdsch. 27(22): [162](#).
Replacement name for *Kuglia* Tutt, [1907].
- [NN] *Superflua* Strand, 1910. Entomol. Rdsch. 27(22): [162](#).
Replacement name for *Kollaria* Tutt, [1907].
- [NN] *Pseudothecla* Strand, 1910. Entomol. Rdsch. 27(22): [162](#).
Replacement name for *Erschoffia* Tutt, [1907].
- [NN] *Thecliolia* Strand, 1910. Entomol. Rdsch. 27(22): [162](#).
Replacement name for *Felderia* Tutt, [1907].
- [JS] *Strymonidia* (*Necovatia*) Verity, [1949]. Var. géogr. saison. pap. diurn. Fr.: 183.
TS: *Papilio acaciae* Fabricius, 1787 by original designation.
- [JS] *Armenia* Dubatolov & Korshunov, 1984. Nov. maloizv. Vidy Fauny Sib. (17): 53.
TS: *Lycaena ledereri* Boisduval, 1848 by original designation.

Satyrium pruni (Linnaeus, 1758)

- [ORIG] *Papilio pruni* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [482](#).
TL: Germany.
- [JS] *Papilio ptorsas* Hufnagel, 1766. Berlin. Mag. 2(1): 68-69.
TL: Berlin (Germany).

Satyrium ilicis (Esper, [1779])

- [ORIG] *Papilio ilicis* Esper, [1779]. Schmett. Abb. Nat. 1(1): [353-354](#) ; [1778]: [pl. 39 \(suppl. 15\), fig. 1b](#) (*P. pruni* var.).
TL: Uffenheim (Bavaria, Germany).
- [JS] *Papilio cerasi* Fabricius, 1787. Mantissa Ins. 1: [69](#).
TL: Austria.
- [JH] *Polyommatus lynceus* Godart, 1823. Tabl. méth. Lépid. Fr.: [47](#).
TL: Europe ; *nec* Drury, 1773.
- [JS] *Papilio cerri* Hübner, [1824]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 175, fig. 863-866](#).
TL: Austria.
- [JS] *Thecla caudatula* Zeller, 1847. Isis von Oken 1847(1): [6-7](#).
TL: Austria.
- [JS] *Thecla lynceus* var. *bischoffii* Gerhard, [1850]. Vers. Monogr. eur. Schmett. (2): [3, pl. 2, fig. 4](#).
TL: Turkey.
- [JS] *Thecla ilicis* var. *cilicica* Holtz, 1897. Illustr. Wochenschr. Entomol. 2: [46](#).
TL: Cilicia (SE Turkey).
- [JS] *Thecla ilicis* race *inalpina* Turati & Verity, 1911. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Ital. 42: [272-273, pl. 1, fig. 12-13](#).
TL: Martigny (Valais, Switzerland).

- [JS] *Thecla ilicis* race *inornata* Turati & Verity, 1911. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Ital. 42: [272-273](#).
TL: Tuscany (Italy).
- [JS] *Thecla ilicis* var. *burdigalensis* Pionneau, 1937. Échange 53(469): 11.
TL: Gironde (E France).
- [JS] *Strymon (Nordmannia) ilicis* s.-race *fiorii* Verity, 1943. Farfalle diurn. Ital. 2: 358, pl. 19 fig. 30-32.
TL: Mesola (Ferrara prov., NE Italy).

Satyrium esculi (Hübner, [1804])

- [ORIG] *Papilio esculi* Hübner, [1804]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 109, fig. 559-560](#), [1806]: [57](#).
TL: Portugal.
- [JS] *Thecla ilicioides* Gerhard, [1850]. Vers. Monogr. eur. Schmett. (3): [3, pl. 4, fig. 5](#).
TL: Ronda (Andalusia, S Spain).
- [JS] *Thecla ilicioides* var. *maculatus* Gerhard, [1850]. Vers. Monogr. eur. Schmett. (3): [3, pl. 4, fig. 4](#).
TL: Andalusia (S Spain).
- [JS] *Thecla ilicis* var. *mauretanica* Staudinger, 1892. Dt. Entomol. Z. 5(2): [279](#).
TL: Tunis (Tunisia) ; Collo, Constantine (NE Algeria).
- [JS] *Thecla esculi* f. *powelli* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. Lépid. comp. 4: [79, 675, pl. 49, fig. 403-404](#).
TL: Khenchela (Algeria).
- [JS] *Strimon esculi* race *camboi* Sagarra, 1926. Butll. Inst. Catal. Hist. nat. (2)6(6): [135-136](#).
TL: Vilamajor (Barcelona prov., NE Spain).
- [JS] *Strimon esculi* race *neglecta* Sagarra, 1926. Butll. Inst. Catal. Hist. nat. (2)6(6): [136](#).
TL: Queralps (Girona prov., NE Spain).
- [JS] *Strymon ilicis pseudoesculi* Bryk, 1940. Arkiv Zool. 32A(22): 19.
TL: Spain.
- [ND] *Nordmannia esculi* ssp. *reisseri* Beuret. In: Bros & Schmidt-Koehl, 1979. Mitt. Entomol. Ges. Basel 29(1) : [12, 16](#).
TL: Xauen (Morocco) ; nomen nudum, published without description.

Satyrium w-album (Knoch, 1782)

- [ORIG] *Papilio w-album* Knoch, 1782. Beitr. Insektengesch. 2: [85-88, pl. 6, fig. 1-2](#).
TL: Leipzig (E Germany).
- [JS] *Papilio cerasi* Fabricius, 1787. Mantissa Ins. 2: [69](#).
TL: Austria.
- [JS] *Papilio w-latinum* Lang, 1789. Verz. Schmett. Gegend. Ausburg (ed. 2): [46](#).
TL: Leipzig (E Germany).
- [JS] *Thecla w-album* var. *meridionalis* Schultz, 1906. Nyt Mag. Naturvidensk. 44: [109-110](#).
TL: Nice, Cannes (SE France).
- [JS] *Thecla w-album* var. *majuscula* Jachontov, 1911. Izv. Kavk. Muz. 5: [313](#).
TL: Borzom (= Borjomi, C Georgia).

Satyrium spini ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)

- [ORIG] *Papilio spini* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775. Ankündigung syst. Werkes Schmett. Wienergegend: [186](#).
TL: Vienna area (Austria).
- [JH] *Papilio lynceus* Esper, [1778]. Schmett. Abb. Nat. 1(1): [pl. 39, fig. 3](#) ; [1779]: [356-357](#).
TL: Germany ; *nec* Drury, 1773. Illustr. Nat. Hist. 1: [12](#), [pl. 7, fig. 1](#), [index](#).
- [JS] *Lycaena melantho* Klug, 1834. Symb. Phys., Ins. 4: [\[40\]](#), [pl. 40, fig. 10-11](#).
TL: Syria.
- [JS] *Thecla spini* var. *major* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. Lépid. comp. 4: [69](#).
TL: Alpes Maritimes (SE France).
- [JS] *Thecla linceus brevicaudis* Vorbrodt & Müller-Rutz, 1911. Schmett. Schweiz 1: [106](#).
TL Zermatt (Valais, Switzerland).
- [JS] *Thecla (Klugia) spini* race *minuta* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(3): [48](#).
TL: Sibillini Mountains (C Italy).
- [JS] *Strymon lynceus* ssp. *anatolicus* Lattin, 1950. Rev. Fac. Sci. Istanbul, Sci. Nat. 15(4): [323, pl. 2, fig. 5](#).
TL: Akşehir (Konya prov., Turkey).

ESU S. vandalusica (Lederer, 1853)

- [ORIG] *Thecla spini* var. *vandalusica* Lederer, 1853. Verh. zool.-bot. Ver. Wien 2 (Abhandl.): [19, 34](#).
TL: Andalusia (S Spain).
- [JS] *Strymon spini* race *bofilli* Sagarra, 1924. Butll. Inst. Catal. Hist. nat. (2)4(9): [200](#).
TL: Albarracin (Aragón, Spain).
- [JS] *Strymon spini* race *leonensis* Manley, 1970. In: Manley & Allcard, Field Guide Butt. Burn. Spain: 114, pl. 35, fig. 29.
TL: Riaño (León prov., N Spain).

Satyrium acaciae (Fabricius, 1787)

- [ORIG] *Papilio acaciae* Fabricius, 1787. Mantissa Ins. 2: [69](#).
TL: S Russia (Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Thecla acaciae* f. *nostras* Courvoisier, 1913. Int. Entomol. Z. 7(38): [252](#).
TL: Europe.
- [JS] *Thecla (Nordmannia) acaciae* race *italica* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(3): [48](#).
TL: Tuscany (Italy).
- [JS] *Strymon acaciae* race *fumosa* Sagarra, 1926. Butll. Inst. Catal. Hist. nat. (2)6(6-7): [135](#).
TL: Queralps (Girona prov., NE Spain).
- [JS] *Strymon (Nordmannia) acaciae* race *frigidior* Verity, 1926. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 38(7/8): [125](#).
TL: Oulx (Piedmont, NW Italy).
- [JS] *Nordmannia guichardi* Higgins, 1965. The Entomologist 98: 10.
TL: Ankara (Turkey).

Satyrium abdominalis (Gerhard, [1850])

[ORIG] *Thecla abdominalis* Gerhard, [1850]. Versuch Monogr. eur. Schmett. (8): [4](#), [pl. 4](#), [fig. 3a-b](#).

TL: Turkey.

[JS] *Thecla acaciae* var. *gerhardi* Staudinger, 1895. Dt. Entomol. Z. 7(2): [241-242](#).

TL: Mardin, Aintab (SE Turkey).

[JS] *Nordmannia elta* Higgins, 1964. The Entomologist 97: 197.

TL: Berlin (Germany).

Satyrium ledereri Rothschild, 1913

[ORIG] *Elycaena ledereri* Boisduval, 1848. Ann. Soc. entomol. Fr. (2)6: [xxix](#).

TL: Khardar (Azerbaijan).

[JS] *Fixsenia ledereri* ssp. *nazeri* Larsen, 1974. Alexanor 8(7): 301.

TL: Jabal Kesrouan (Lebanon).

[JS] *Satyrium ledereri* ssp. *christianae* Olivier, 1989. Phegea 17(1): [8-12](#), [fig. 7-12](#).

TL: Mt. Karvoúni (Samos Isl., Greece).

Conclusion

This synonymic list offers a foundation for the taxonomy of Western Palearctic Pieridae.

By linking each name to its original description, it enhances transparency, accessibility, and historical accuracy. However, the list is not yet complete, and gaps remain in both hyperlinks and taxonomic data. Researchers, lepidopterists and enthusiasts are warmly invited to contribute by submitting missing hyperlinks, overlooked synonyms, or other relevant information.

Author contribution

Michel Taymans: conceptualisation, analysis, visualisation, writing - original draft, writing – review and editing.

Sylvain Cuvelier: analysis, validation, visualisation, writing – review and editing.

Toward a revised checklist of the Western Palearctic butterflies, hyperlinked to the original descriptions at species, genus and family level (Lepidoptera, Papilionoidea)

Part V: Rationale and framework for the Lycaenidae (part II)

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Abstract

This second review of taxonomic and nomenclatural issues in Lycaenidae examines the status of family-group names in the light of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN), historical classification schemes, recent phylogenetic evidence, and current usage. Emphasis is placed on the classification of subfamilies and tribes, for which conflicts among older names, synonymies, and prevailing usage have required rigorous assessment under the Code.

The classification of all species within the genera and subgenera of the subfamily Polyommatae, excluding the tribe Polyommataini (which will be addressed in a future contribution), is critically reviewed and justified. Particular emphasis is placed on the generic classification of the tribe Scolitantidini, for which alternative taxonomic arrangements have been proposed and remain contentious.

Key words

Taxonomy — Checklist — Papilionoidea — Lycaenidae — Lycaeninae — Theclinae — Polyommatae — Polyommataini — Lampidini — Celastrini — Scolitantidini — Everini — Zizeerini — Azanini (tribe proposed) — Phengarina (subtribe proposed) — Palaeophilota (subtribe proposed) — *Leptotes* — *Cyclyrius* — *Azanus* — *Lampides* — *Cacyreus* — *Celastrina* — *Tarucus* — *Phengaris* — *Maculinea* — *Pseudophengaris* (genus proposed) — *Turanana* — *Pseudophilotes* — *Palaeophilotes* — *Scolitantides* — *Iolana* — *Glaucopsyche* — *Zizeeria* — *Zizina* — *Cupido* — ESU — *Cigaritis estherae* — *Lycaena heracleana* — *Satyrium vandalousica* — Western Palearctic.

Introduction

The present article aims to clarify and justify the classification adopted in the checklist for the subfamily Polyommatae of the family Lycaenidae, with the exception of the tribe Polyommataini, which will be treated in a subsequent paper. Despite extensive taxonomic and phylogenetic research, the internal classification of Lycaenidae remains only partially resolved. In particular, the rank and delimitation of the major lineages traditionally recognised as subfamilies have been interpreted differently by various authors, reflecting differences in the morphological, molecular, and combined datasets on which their conclusions are based. As a result, alternative classifications continue to coexist in the literature, and some aspects of the higher-level taxonomy of the family remain subjects of ongoing debate.

Over the past decades, numerous phylogenetic studies have advanced competing hypotheses concerning the relationships among these groups. Analyses based on morphological characters, molecular data, or combinations of both have yielded alternative arrangements of the major clades and have often assigned them different taxonomic ranks, recognising them either as subfamilies or as tribes within more inclusive classifications. As a consequence, no single classification has gained universal acceptance, and the circumscription, placement, and relationships of several groups remain subjects of ongoing debate. In addition, some recent phylogenetic studies have proposed generic delimitations based primarily on molecular evidence, with limited consideration of morphological, ecological, biogeographical, or nomenclatural criteria. Although such approaches have provided valuable insights into evolutionary relationships, they may also contribute to nomenclatural instability when taxonomic changes are introduced without sufficient integration of other lines of evidence.

1. Classification of of tribes, subtribes, genera and subgenera within the subfamily Polyommatainae

1.1 Introduction - Taxonomic approach adopted in the present work

Recent phylogenetic studies have considerably improved our understanding of evolutionary relationships within the subfamily Polyommatainae. However, the translation of phylogenetic hypotheses into a practical and stable taxonomic classification remains a matter of debate. In several instances, the strict application of monophyly as the primary criterion for generic delimitation has led to the synonymisation of long-established genera or to the transfer of numerous species between genera. While such changes may reflect inferred evolutionary relationships more accurately, they can also result in substantial nomenclatural instability and reduce the continuity and practical utility of traditional classifications.

The classification adopted herein is guided by three complementary objectives: (1) the recognition of monophyletic taxa, (2) the explicit representation of the principal evolutionary lineages recovered by recent phylogenetic studies, and (3) the preservation of nomenclatural stability whenever compatible with the preceding objectives. The aim is to achieve a classification that reflects current knowledge of phylogenetic relationships while maintaining a practical and stable taxonomic framework.

In some cases, the recognition of previously unnamed monophyletic clades may require the establishment of new suprageneric taxa. However, such changes are generally limited in scope and have a considerably smaller impact on nomenclatural stability than the widespread synonymisation of genera. Another potential drawback of extensive generic synonymisation is the loss of diagnosability. Although the resulting genera may satisfy the criterion of monophyly, they may become morphologically heterogeneous and difficult to characterise using traditional taxonomic characters. In some instances, no clear diagnostic features remain other than those derived from molecular data, and species exhibiting markedly different external morphology, genital structures, or biological traits may be placed within the same genus. While such classifications may accurately reflect phylogenetic relationships, they can reduce the practical and descriptive value of generic taxa for taxonomists, ecologists, and conservation biologists.

The advantages of this approach are illustrated by two well-known cases within the subfamily Polyommatainae. The synonymisation of *Maculinea* under *Phengaris* and the placement of *Palaeophilotes* within *Pseudophilotes* have resulted in substantial nomenclatural changes, despite the recognition of clearly distinct evolutionary lineages. By making fuller use of intermediate taxonomic ranks, particularly tribes and subtribes, and, where appropriate, subgenera, it becomes possible to accommodate phylogenetic evidence without unnecessarily suppressing long-established generic names.

The classification proposed in the present work should therefore be regarded as a compromise between phylogenetic accuracy and nomenclatural stability. Its primary objective is not merely to assign names to clades but to provide a hierarchical framework that remains both informative and practical for future taxonomic, faunistic, and conservation studies.

It should be emphasised that the classification proposed herein is intended as a provisional framework based on currently available phylogenetic evidence. Ongoing phylogenomic initiatives and future large-scale studies will undoubtedly provide a more detailed understanding of relationships within the subfamily Polyommatainae and may necessitate the revision of some of the taxonomic arrangements adopted in the present work.

In particular, initiatives such as the Lepidoptera Tree of Life project (PSYCHE), which aim to generate extensive genomic datasets across the diversity of Lepidoptera, are expected to clarify relationships among several currently unresolved lineages. Consequently, the classification proposed herein should not be regarded as definitive, but rather as a practical and phylogenetically informed working hypothesis that can be readily updated as new evidence becomes available.

1.2 Historical and taxonomic context

The suprageneric classification of the Polyommatainae has undergone substantial changes over the past decades, reflecting the transition from morphology-based systems to phylogenetic hypotheses inferred from molecular data.

In his influential classification of the Lycaenidae, Eliot (1973) recognised four tribes within the Polyommatainae: Candalidini, Lycaenesthini, Niphandini, and Polyommatini. The first three tribes include relatively few genera and species and are not represented in the West Palearctic fauna. In contrast, Polyommatini comprises a large number of genera and species, most of which occur in the Palearctic region. To facilitate their classification, Eliot subdivided Polyommatini into several informal sections corresponding to limited groups of genera, which may be regarded as equivalent to subtribes. These sections were primarily defined on the basis of morphological characters, including wing venation, external morphology, and genital structures.

Restricting his study to the European and North African fauna, Higgins (1975) proposed a different arrangement, dividing the Polyommatainae into six tribes. The genera were distributed as follows:

Lampidini: *Tarucus*, *Syntarucus* (= *Leptotes*), *Cyclurius*, *Lampides*.

Everini: *Azanus*, *Cupido*, *Everes*.

Zizeerini: *Zizeeria*.

Scolitantidini: *Pseudophilotes*, *Scolitantides*, *Glaucopsyche*, *Maculinea*, *Iolana*, *Turanana*.

Celastrini: *Celastrina*.

Subsequent catalogues largely followed Higgins's arrangement, with only minor modifications. Vives Moreno (1994) placed *Cacyreus*, a genus not yet established in the European fauna at the time of Higgins's work, within Lampidini and recognised a separate tribe, Tarucini, for *Tarucus*. Leraut (1997), on the other hand, transferred *Celastrina* to Everini.

Since then, numerous phylogenetic studies have investigated the relationships among Polyommatainae genera, leading to several alternative classifications. Two recent large-scale phylogenetic analyses, one focused on the European fauna (Wiemers *et al.* 2020) and the other based on worldwide sampling of Papilionoidea (Kawahara *et al.* 2023), provide particularly useful frameworks for evaluating the suprageneric classification of the group.

Wiemers *et al.* (2020) presented a comprehensive phylogenetic hypothesis for the European butterfly fauna. Although the authors did not propose a formal tribal classification within Polyommatainae, their phylogenetic tree reveals several well-supported lineages corresponding to the following assemblages:

- A: *Azanus*
- B: *Zizeeria, Tarucus*
Celastrina, Lampides, Cacyreus
Phengaris
Scolithantides, Praephilotes, Iolana, Glaucoopsyche
Turanana, Pseudophilotes
- C: *Leptodes, Cyclyrius*
- D: *Tongeia, Cupido*
- E: Polyommata

In contrast, Kawahara *et al.* (2023), based on a much broader worldwide sampling, recognised three tribes within the Polyommatae: Lycaenesthini, Niphandini, and Polyommataini. The first two tribes contain only a limited number of genera and are absent from the West Palaearctic fauna. The large tribe Polyommataini includes the majority of West Palaearctic taxa and is structured as follows:

- A: *Azanus*
- B: *Cupido, Tongeia, Luthrodes*
- C: Polyommata
- D: *Leptodes, Cyclyrius, Cacyreus, Lampides*
- E: *Pseudophilotes, Turanana*
Phengaris
Scolithantides
Iolana, Glaucoopsyche
- F: *Celastrina*
- G: *Zizina, Zizeeria*
Tarucus

1.3. Conclusion

As higher taxonomic ranks are intended to reflect different levels of relationship within a phylogenetic framework, the subfamily Polyommatae is herein subdivided into several tribes. The alternative approach, consisting of recognising only three tribes, with Lycaenesthini and Niphandini containing relatively few species and Polyommataini encompassing the vast majority of taxa, greatly limits the ability of expressing phylogenetic relationships through lower-ranking subdivisions. Such a classification fails to adequately reflect several well-supported lineages revealed by both morphological and molecular studies.

Based on the phylogenetic evidence currently available, it remains premature to propose a definitive suprageneric classification of the subfamily Polyommatae. Nevertheless, several recurring patterns emerge from the studies discussed above and provide a basis for the following provisional arrangement.

Azanus consistently appears as part of a distinct lineage associated with several non-West Palaearctic genera. As no currently available tribal name appears suitable for this group, the genus is provisionally assigned to **Azanini** (proposed tribe).

Cupido and *Tongeia* are closely related genera and are therefore placed in **Everini**. Although their precise position within the subfamily remains uncertain, both recent phylogenetic studies recover them near the core Polyommataini lineage. To maintain monophyletic groups, *Luthrodes* is provisionally excluded from Everini and treated together with Polyommataini; its placement will be discussed in a subsequent paper.

Leptodes and *Cyclyrius* on the one hand, and *Cacyreus* and *Lampides* on the other, form two closely related pairs of genera. Wiemers *et al.* (2020) recovered these pairs as relatively distant lineages, whereas Kawahara *et al.* (2023) placed them within a common clade. Pending further phylogenomic studies, these four genera are provisionally grouped within **Lampidini**.

All recent phylogenetic studies consistently recover *Pseudophilotes*, *Turanana*, *Phengaris*, *Scolithantides*, *Iolana* and *Glaucoopsyche* as closely related genera. They are therefore assigned to **Scolitantidini**.

The position of *Celastrina* remains particularly uncertain. Wiemers *et al.* (2020) recovered the genus close to *Lampides*, whereas Kawahara *et al.* (2023) placed it within a distinct clade together with numerous non-Palaearctic taxa. Pending further studies, *Celastrina* is provisionally retained within a separate tribe, **Celastrini**.

Finally, *Zizina*, *Zizeeria* and *Tarucus* form a well-supported lineage and are consequently grouped within **Zizeerini**.

The classification proposed herein, recognising a relatively large number of tribes within the Polyommatae, is fully compatible with the principle of monophyly as inferred from the phylogenetic hypothesis of Kawahara *et al.* (2023). It also provides a practical framework for recognising subtribes grouping closely related genera.

A limitation of several recent classifications is the synonymisation of numerous traditionally recognised genera, which are consequently reduced to subgeneric rank. The broader use of the intermediate rank of subtribe, as adopted herein, makes it possible to retain these genera while simultaneously preserving monophyletic suprageneric groups. As demonstrated in the following chapters, this approach reduces unnecessary nomenclatural changes and contributes to a more stable and informative classification.

1.4. Proposed tribe Azanini

This tribe-level lineage corresponds to the clade recovered in the phylogenomic tree *A Time-Calibrated Global Phylogeny of Butterflies* by Kawahara *et al.* (2023), between:

BN003936_KD94S033_Lycaenidae_Polyommatainae_Polyommataini_Neolucia_agricola

and
BN007150_DL18S337_Lycaenidae_Polyommatainae_Polyommataini_Danis_danis

The limits and diagnosis of this lineage remain provisional and should be refined by future phylogenomic studies before any formal nomenclatural action is undertaken.

Type genus: *Azanus* Moore, 1881.

Currently included genera: *Neolucia*, *Sahulana*, *Theclinesstes*, *Azanus*, *Petrelaea*, *Pseudonacaduba*, *Orthomiella*, *Una*, *Ionolyce*, etc.

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2. *Phengaris* Doherty, 1891 and *Maculinea* Eecke, 1915 (Lycaenidae): nomenclatural and taxonomic considerations

2.1. Historical Taxonomic Framework and Phylogenetic Evidence

Prior to 2007, all Palearctic species of this group, including *alcon*, *nausithous*, *teleius*, *arion* and related taxa, were traditionally assigned to the genus *Maculinea*. This genus was characterised by a relatively homogeneous external morphology, notably the predominantly blue coloration of the male upperside and the characteristic arrangement of markings on the brownish underside. In contrast, the Oriental and eastern Palearctic species, including *daitozana*, *atroguttata* and *albida*, were assigned to the genus *Phengaris*, whose species share a distinct habitus characterised by a pale to whitish dorsal surface and a characteristic arrangement of ventral markings on a whitish underside.

In a phylogenetic study of the group, Fric *et al.* (2007) concluded that *Maculinea* and *Phengaris* should be treated as a single genus. Their proposal was based primarily on the principle of monophyly. Molecular analyses indicated that the species traditionally assigned to *Maculinea* did not form a lineage distinct from *Phengaris* but rather were embedded within the same evolutionary clade. The resulting phylogenetic hypothesis can be summarised as follows:

A + (B + C)

where:

A = *Maculinea alcon* + *rebeli*

B = *Phengaris daitozana* + (*atroguttata* + *albida*)

C = (*Maculinea nausithous* + *teleius*) + *arion*

Under this hypothesis, the recognition of *Maculinea* and *Phengaris* as separate genera would render one of the genera paraphyletic.

The phylogenetic study of Ugelvig *et al.* (2011) produced a somewhat different topology. In this analysis, the species traditionally assigned to *Maculinea* formed a more homogeneous lineage and were not intermingled with the species assigned to *Phengaris*. Furthermore, the genus *Caerulea* was recovered as part of the same broader clade, according to the following structure: In contrast, Kawahara *et al.* (2023), based on a much broader worldwide sampling, recognised three tribes within the Polyommatinae: Lycaenesthini, Niphandini, and Polyommadini. The first two tribes contain only a limited number of genera and are absent from the West Palaearctic fauna. The large tribe Polyommadini includes the majority of West Palaearctic taxa and is structured as follows:

A + (B + (C + (D + E)))

where:

- A = *Azanus*
- B = *Cupido*, *Tongeia*, *Luthrodes*
- C = Polyommatina
- D = *Leptodes*, *Cyclyrius*, *Cacyreus*, *Lampides*
- E = *Pseudophilotes*, *Turanana*
Phengaris
Scolithantides
Iolana, *Glaucoopsyche*
- F = *Celastrina*
- G = *Zizina*, *Zizeeria*
Tarucus

2.2. Taxonomic Interpretation and Provisional Classification

Pending the availability of such data, and following the principles outlined in the previous chapter, *Maculinea* is provisionally retained as a distinct genus in the present checklist. Together with *Phengaris* and *Caerulea*, it is assigned to the new subtribe Phengarina (subtribe proposed) within the tribe Scolitantidini.

Under the phylogenetic hypothesis proposed by Ugelvig *et al.* (2011), the maintenance of monophyletic genera would nevertheless require the recognition of an additional generic entity corresponding to clade B. Should this topology be confirmed by future studies, the resulting classification would comprise four genera arranged as follows:

A = *Caerulea*; B = *Pseudophengaris* (genus proposed); C = *Phengaris*; D+E = *Maculinea*.

Such an arrangement would preserve both the monophyly of all recognised genera and the long-established usage of the generic name *Maculinea*, while minimising nomenclatural changes within the group.

2.3. Proposed subtribe Phengarina

This subtribe-level lineage corresponds to the clade recovered in the phylogenomic tree *A Time-Calibrated Global Phylogeny of Butterflies* of Kawahara *et al.* (2023), defined as extending from: BN004046_FH05M001_Lycaenidae_Polyommatinae_Polyommadini_Caerulea_coeligena and BN006335_AD00P068_Lycaenidae_Polyommatinae_Polyommadini_Phengaris_nausithous

This lineage belongs to the tribe Scolitantidini, which in the same phylogeny corresponds to the clade spanning from:

BN003925_AS92Z401_Lycaenidae_Polyommatinae_Polyommadini_Euphilotes_enoptes

to

BN002858_LEP31611_Lycaenidae_Polyommatinae_Polyommadini_Glaucoopsyche_lygdamus

The limits and diagnosis of this lineage remain provisional and should be refined by future phylogenomic studies before any formal nomenclatural action is undertaken.

Type genus: *Phengaris* Doherty, 1891. Currently included genera: *Caerulea*, *Phengaris*, *Maculinea*, etc.

Currently included genera: *Caerulea*, *Phengaris*, *Maculinea*, etc.

The subtribal groupings proposed herein are intended as provisional classificatory units that reflect current phylogenetic hypotheses. Their circumscription and diagnostic characters remain incompletely resolved, and the descriptions provided should not be interpreted as formal diagnoses. Additional phylogenetic, morphological, and biological evidence will be required to establish stable limits and comprehensive diagnoses for these lineages. Consequently, the proposed subtribal names are introduced only as provisional frameworks for discussing evolutionary relationships and remain subject to revision as new data become available.

2.4. Proposed genus *Pseudophengaris*

This genus lineage corresponds to the clade recovered in the phylogenomic tree of Ugelvig *et al.* (2011) for the species *Phengaris daitozana* Wileman, 1908.

Type species: *Phengaris daitozana* Wileman, 1908.

Currently included species: *Phengaris daitozana* Wileman, 1908.

The genus-group classifications proposed herein are intended as provisional units to facilitate interpretation of currently available phylogenetic hypotheses. They do not constitute formal diagnoses under the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN). The limits, composition, and diagnostic characters of several lineages remain insufficiently resolved and will require further phylogenetic, morphological, and biological study before robust diagnoses can be established. Accordingly, the proposed genus-group names are provided as practical tools for discussing phylogenetic relationships and should be regarded as provisional pending future systematic revision.

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2.5. References

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3. *Pseudophilotes* Beuret, 1958 and *Palaeophilotes* Forster, 1938 (Lycaenidae): nomenclatural and taxonomic considerations

3.1. Phylogenetic context and taxonomic conflict

Zhang *et al.* (2023) conducted a detailed phylogenetic study of the tribe Scolitantidini. Their results revealed a very low genetic divergence (approximately 2.1%) between *Palaeophilotes triphysina*, the type species of *Palaeophilotes* Forster, 1938, and *Pseudophilotes baton*, the type species of *Pseudophilotes* Beuret, 1958. In contrast, *bavius*, traditionally assigned to the subgenus *Rubrapterus*, was recovered as a more distinct lineage within the same complex.

Based on these results, Zhang *et al.* (2023) concluded that the taxa traditionally treated as *Palaeophilotes* and *Pseudophilotes* should be regarded as congeneric. However, in view of the relatively rapid evolution of the nuclear genome and the phylogenetic structure recovered in their analyses, the authors proposed retaining *Pseudophilotes* and *Rubrapterus* as subgenera within *Palaeophilotes* rather than placing them in complete synonymy.

Although phylogenetically consistent, this solution would result in substantial nomenclatural changes, particularly through the replacement of the well-established generic name *Pseudophilotes* by *Palaeophilotes* for a number of widely known species.

An alternative approach is proposed herein. Rather than modifying the generic nomenclature, phylogenetic relationships may be expressed through the use of suprageneric ranks, particularly subtribes. Such an approach is difficult to implement in classifications recognising only a single West Palaearctic tribe, Polyommataini, because the extensive use of subtribes within such a broad taxonomic unit rapidly becomes impractical. However, the multi-tribal classification adopted in the present work provides a more suitable framework for the recognition of phylogenetically meaningful subtribes.

3.2. Nomenclatural Implications and Alternative Interpretations

An alternative approach is proposed herein. Rather than modifying the generic nomenclature, phylogenetic relationships may be expressed through the use of suprageneric ranks, particularly subtribes. Such an approach is difficult to implement in classifications recognising only a single West Palaearctic tribe, Polyommataini, because the extensive use of subtribes within such a broad taxonomic unit rapidly becomes impractical. However, the multi-tribal classification adopted in the present work provides a more suitable framework for the recognition of phylogenetically meaningful subtribes. Furthermore, additional molecular studies are still required. Several taxa closely related to this complex have not yet been adequately sampled, and their inclusion may significantly modify the inferred relationships. The phylogenomic tree published by Kawahara *et al.* (2023) already suggests that other genera may belong to the same evolutionary lineage. The phylogenetic placement of the genera *Euphilotes* and *Philotiella* remains uncertain. While Zhang *et al.* (2023) recovered these genera within the *Palaeophilotes–Pseudophilotes* clade in the mitochondrial tree, they appear as a distinct lineage in both the nuclear and chromosomal trees. Pending further investigations, this apparent incongruence should be regarded as unresolved and may have implications for the future classification of the group.

Pending the availability of more comprehensive phylogenetic data, *Palaeophilotes*, *Pseudophilotes*, *Rubrapterus* and *Turanana* are provisionally retained as distinct genera and placed within the new subtribe **Palaeophilotina** (proposed subtribe) of the tribe Scolitantidini.

The resulting phylogenetic structure may be summarised as follows:

A + (B + (C + D))

where:

A = *Turanana*

B = *Rubrapterus*

C = *Palaeophilotes*

D = *Pseudophilotes*

This arrangement preserves the monophyly of the group while minimising nomenclatural disruption and maintaining the long-established generic names currently used in the taxonomic literature. It also provides a flexible framework that can readily accommodate future phylogenetic results without requiring major changes to generic nomenclature.

3.3. Proposed subtribe Palaeophilotina

This subtribe-level lineage corresponds to the clade recovered in the phylogenomic tree *A Time-Calibrated Global Phylogeny of Butterflies* of Kawahara *et al.* (2023), defined as extending between:

BN001321_LEP50916_Lycaenidae_Polyommatainae_Polyommataini_Scolitantides_vicrama [= *Pseudophilotes vicrama*]

and

BN005598_RI18W078_Lycaenidae_Polyommatainae_Polyommataini_Micropsyche_ariana

This lineage is assigned to the tribe Scolitantidini, which in the same phylogeny corresponds to the clade spanning from:

BN003925_AS922401_Lycaenidae_Polyommatainae_Polyommataini_Euphilotes_enoptes

to

BN002858_LEP31611_Lycaenidae_Polyommatainae_Polyommataini_Glaucopsyche_lygdamus

The limits and diagnosis of this lineage remain provisional and should be refined by future phylogenomic studies prior to any formal nomenclatural action.

Type genus: *Palaeophilotes* Forster, 1938.

Currently included genera: *Turanana*, *Rubrapterus*, *Palaeophilotes*, *Pseudophilotes*, etc.

The subtribal groupings proposed herein are intended as provisional classificatory units designed to facilitate the interpretation of currently available phylogenetic hypotheses. They should not be regarded as formal diagnoses under the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN). In particular, the limits, composition, and diagnostic characters of several lineages remain insufficiently resolved and will require further phylogenetic, morphological, and biological study before robust diagnoses can be established. Accordingly, the proposed subtribal names are introduced solely as practical tools for discussing phylogenetic relationships and are to be regarded as provisional pending future systematic revision.

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4. Addition of Evolutionarily Significant Units (ESU) to the Checklist

4.1. ESU *Cigaritis estherae* Brévignon, 1985

Pending a more comprehensive integrative study of the entire group, *Cigaritis estherae* is provisionally regarded herein as an Evolutionarily Significant Unit (ESU), following the detailed study by Tarrier *et al.* (2026), which supported its recognition as a distinct species on the basis of biogeographical, biological, and mitochondrial genetic evidence, while also noting that the observed genetic divergence was relatively limited and subject to alternative interpretation.

Reference

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4.2. ESU *Lycaena heracleana* (Blachier, 1908)

Pending further integrative taxonomic studies, the Moroccan populations currently assigned to *Lycaena alciphron heracleana* are provisionally regarded as a distinct Evolutionarily Significant Unit (ESU). This treatment is based on their mitochondrial genetic divergence (Dapporto *et al.*, 2022: [139, figs 255–256](#); Wiemers, 2003: [48, fig. 34](#)) and their marked geographic isolation from other *L. alciphron* populations, separated by more than 500 km.

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4.3. ESU *Satyrrium vandalusica* (Lederer, 1853)

The taxon *vandalusica* is here regarded as a potential Evolutionarily Significant Unit (ESU), based on the marked genetic divergence identified by Dapporto *et al.* (2022) within *S. spini*, between Spanish populations and those occurring elsewhere in Europe.

However, confirmation of this status will require further integrative research combining ecological and morphological evidence with higher-resolution genomic approaches, preferably based on whole-genome data.

Reference

Dapporto L., Menchetti M., Vodă R., Corbella C., Cuvelier S., Djemadi I., Gascoigne-Pees M., Hinojosa J., Lam N., Serracanta M., Talavera G., Dincă V. & Vila. R. 2022. The Atlas of mitochondrial genetic diversity for Western Palearctic butterflies. — *Global Ecology and Biogeography*. 00, 1–7. doi.org/10.1111/geb.13579 ([url Atlas appendix S1](#))

Author contribution

Michel Taymans: conceptualisation, analysis, visualisation, writing - original draft, writing – review and editing.

Sylvain Cuvelier: analysis, validation, visualisation, writing – review and editing.

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Second confirmed locality of *Kirinia climene* (Esper, [1783]) in Albania: Mount Pashtrik, with notes on its distribution in the Balkans and the Republic of Moldova.

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Abstract

Kirinia climene (Esper, [1783]) is a rarely recorded Satyrinae butterfly distributed from the Middle East to the Balkans. In Albania, it was previously known from a historical record from Mount Pashtrik. In 2023, Cuvelier and Dincă reported the species near Lake Prespa, and here we add a second confirmed locality for Albania, based on a 2025 specimen from Mount Pashtrik (1.600 m a.s.l.), confirming its persistence after more than a century. Its Balkan distribution remains fragmented, with strongholds in Serbia and northern Greece, and only historical records in Romania (Banat) and the Republic of Moldova.

Key words

Kirinia climene — Papilionoidea — Nymphalidae — Satyrinae — distribution — conservation — Mount Pashtrik — Albania — Balkans.

Introduction

Mount Pashtrik (Mali i Pashtrikut) is a limestone massif situated along the border between north-eastern Albania and south-western Kosovo, north of the Drin River and southeast of the Northern Albanian Alps. Part of the southern extension of the Dinaric Alps, it rises to 1.986 m between the White Drin valley in Kosovo and the Has region in Albania. South of Pashtrik lie Mount Koritnik (2.380 m), Djalica e Lumës (2.484 m), and the Korab range, including Mount Korab (2.764 m), the highest peak in Albania. Geologically, Pashtrik consists mainly of Triassic and Jurassic limestones and dolomites, with well-developed karst features such as rocky outcrops, sinkholes, and fissures. Its rugged terrain supports a mosaic of habitats ranging from dry grasslands and shrublands to montane forests.

Located at the transition between Mediterranean and continental climatic zones, Mount Pashtrik harbours a rich biodiversity and numerous Balkan endemic and relict species, making it an important biodiversity hotspot in the Albania–Kosovo border region.

Kirinia climene (Esper, [1783]) has a distribution extending from the Middle East through Ukraine and the Republic of Moldova to the Balkans (Tshikolovets 2011), where it is infrequently recorded and occupies geographically isolated habitats.

K. climene is a thermophilous woodland butterfly that typically inhabits open deciduous woodland, woodland edges, clearings and other ecotonal habitats with a well-developed herb layer. Adults are relatively sedentary and often remain within shaded woodland, where they can be difficult to detect. During hot weather, individuals frequently rest and bask on tree trunks, a behaviour that may further reduce their detectability. Field identification may also be hindered by its superficial resemblance to the much more common *Maniola jurtina* (Linnaeus, 1758), particularly when individuals are observed only briefly in flight. These ecological and behavioural characteristics likely contribute to the apparent rarity of *K. climene* and may explain why it is infrequently recorded even in suitable habitats. Consequently, the currently known distribution of the species in south-western Europe is probably incomplete, and the number of occupied localities may be underestimated owing to imperfect detectability rather than true absence.

In Rebel & Zerny (1931, p 75), a worn female of *K. climene* was reported from Albania, near Krumë on the south-western foothills of Mount Pashtrik (Fig. 1a). The specimen was collected by participants of the 1918 expedition, namely Penther, Predota and Zerny. Details of the locality were provided on page 46 of the original publication and are reproduced in Fig. 1b.

*85. *Pararge clymene* Esp.

Kruma 8. VIII., ein stark abgeflogenes ♀ (P. Z.).

Mazedonien: Skoplje (Häussler) (ob richtig?).

Südlichste bisher bekannte Fundorte auf der westlichen
Balkanhalbinsel.

trosta signalis, *Cleophana olivina*) in der subalpinen Zone zusammen mit alpinen Arten. Auch bei Kruma am Südwestfuße des Bështriq, das etwa 800 m hoch liegen dürfte, sammelten wir mehrmals und fanden dort unter andern *Pararge clymene* und eine neue Form von *Pyrausta quadripunctalis*.

Fig. 1a. First published record of *K. clymene* from Albania (Rebel & Zerny 1931, p. 75)

Fig. 1b. Original description of the collecting locality of the first Albanian record of *K. clymene* (Rebel & Zerny 1931, p. 46).

Subsequent faunistic studies from the Kosovar side of Mount Pashtrik (Jakšić 2007; Mustafa *et al.* 2015) did not record *K. clymene*.

On 13 July 2022, Cuvelier and Dincă (Cuvelier *et al.* 2023) recorded several worn individuals of *K. clymene* west of Liqeni i Prespës in Prespa National Park, establishing a second, geographically distant locality for the species in Albania. This population is continuous with adjacent populations in the Republic of North Macedonia. For a more comprehensive account of the occurrence and ecology of *Kirinia clymene* in the Lake Prespa region, see ([url](#)).

Confirmed presence of *Kirinia clymene* on Mount Pashtrik (2025)

On 27.vii.2025, a single worn specimen of *K. clymene* (Esper, [1783]) was collected (Fig. 2a-b) at 1.600 m a.s.l. at 42.21N, 20.50E, at the forest edge between deciduous woodland and tall herbaceous grassland (Fig. 3-6). The activity was authorized under Permit No. 329/1 of 28.i.2025, issued by the Agjencia Kombëtare e Zonave të Mbrojtura, Drejtoria e Menaxhimit, Monitorimit dhe Regjistrimit të Zonave të Mbrojtura. The specimen is currently deposited in the author's reference collection.

The most recent distribution map (Fig. 7) of *K. clymene* in Albania is provided in *Chronicles Fluturat e Shqipërisë* (Cuvelier & Papparisto 2026), available at ([url](#)).

Fig. 2a-b. Upper- and underside of the collected *K. clymene*. Mount Pashtrik, (Albania), 1.600 m a.s.l., 27.vii.2025. (Collector: Sylvain Cuvelier)

Fig. 3. View to Mount Pashtrik from Cabani, 27.vii.2025. (Photographer: Sylvain Cuvelier)
edge between deciduous woodland and tall herbaceous grassland. (Photographer: Sylvain Cuvelier)

Fig. 4. View from 1.500 m a.s.l. on Mount Pashtrik, showing the higher-elevation habitat consisting of the forest

Fig. 5-6. Forest edge between deciduous woodland and tall herbaceous grassland at 1.600 m a.s.l. where *K. climene* was collected. (Photographer: Sylvain Cuvelier)

Fig. 7. Updated distribution map of *K. climene* in Albania. Historical data New observations since 2018. (Cuvelier & Paparisto 30.iv.2026)

Fig. 8. Distribution map of *K. climene* in Balkans and Republic of Moldova.

Green dot: confirmed *K. climene* on Mt. Pashtrik; pale yellow dots: Balkan records; red dots: historical but unconfirmed records from Romania and the Republic of Moldova. (Cuvelier 2026)

Notes on the distribution in the Balkans and the Republic of Moldova

Concerning the Republic of Moldova, since Miller & Zubowsky (1908), who reported *Kirinia climene* (Esper, [1783]) from Tighina (Bender, Bendery) in Bessarabia, now the Republic of Moldova, no further confirmed records of the species are known to the author.

In Romania, the situation is as follows. Most known specimens of *Kirinia climene* (Esper, 1783) from southern Banat (present-day Romania) were collected during the nineteenth century. The species was first reported from Mehadia by the Viennese entomologist Georg Dahl in 1822 (Rebel, 1911). Nearly all specimens currently preserved in the major European museum collections of Vienna, London, and Budapest predate 1900, with collection records from 1822, 1876, 1879, 1881, 1882, 1893, 1896, and 1897. These specimens originate from the collections of Dahl, Pavel, Fountaine, Viertl, Bohatsch, Reichel, Dahlström, and Tomala, and were collected at Băile Herculane, Muntele Domogled, Pecinișca, Orșova, Dealul Alion (Alion Hill), and Mehadia. During the same period, *K. climene* was also reported from Turnu Severin (Caradja 1895–1896). The most recent published records documenting the occurrence of *K. climene* in the Băile Herculane area date to 1910, based on observations reported by Keynes and Keynes (1911). Following these records, no further confirmed occurrences from the region appear to have been published for many decades.

Levente (2024) suggests that insect abundance has declined drastically in Romania, while species loss appears limited, with a possible maximum of around ten Lepidoptera species considered to have disappeared, including *K. climene*.

With regard to its distribution in Hungary, some confusion remains to be clarified. Gozmány (1968, p. 171) stated that *K. climene* does not occur in the country, whereas Higgins & Riley (1970, p. 270) reported the species from eastern Hungary. However, this most likely refers to older literature in which localities such as Siebenbürgen, the Banat frontier, Herculesbad, and Orsova were historically placed within eastern Hungary.

In Serbia, *K. climene* was previously known from only two localities prior to 2011. Durić & Popović (2011) subsequently added three additional records, and more recent surveys have further confirmed its occurrence in the country. Distribution data derived from GBIF and personal observations corroborate its presence in eastern Serbia, where suitable habitats appear to be widespread and currently not under threat, indicating that this region represents one of the European strongholds for the species.

For a long time, the occurrence of *K. climene* in Bulgaria remained doubtful or poorly documented. Essayan & Jugan (1993), provided the first well-documented records of *K. climene* in Bulgaria. Kolev (2003) confirmed its presence by documenting two localities and reviewing historical records. Since then, additional observations and records have helped to clarify its distribution and support its continued occurrence in the country. In Bulgaria, adjacent areas along the Serbian border also harbour records of *K. climene*, with additional isolated occurrences near the Greek border and in the Sinite Kamûni massif north of Sliven.

A recent record in Observado, dated 08.vi.2019, from a lowland locality (<200 m a.s.l.) in the Haskovo District (south-eastern Bulgaria) lies considerably outside the currently confirmed range of the species in Bulgaria. However, in the absence of photographic documentation and given the atypically low-altitude habitat, this record should be treated with caution and regarded as requiring confirmation. For this reason, it was not included in Fig. 8.

In Greece, the species was first recorded by Willemse (1977) from the Trikala district. Current distribution data kindly provided by L. Pamperis, and based on coarse 10 × 10 km grid records, indicate that the northern Pindos region represents a second major European stronghold for *K. climene*, with additional isolated populations occurring further south in the Pindos and in north-eastern Greece. Schaider & Jakšić (1989) presented a distribution map of *K. climene* indicating only five disjunct localities. In the Republic of North Macedonia, the species is known from a small number of isolated records and has been reported only sporadically, although it appears to occur more consistently in border regions adjacent to Greece and Albania, particularly in the wider Lake Prespa area. As noted in this study, *K. climene* has not been recorded from the Kosovar side of Mount Pashtrik or from the country as a whole. However, the presence of similar habitats on the Kosovar side of the massif makes its occurrence in Kosovo highly plausible, at least in this area.

Based on published sources, database records, personal observations, and the present study, a distribution map (Fig. 8) was compiled to illustrate the overall range of *K. climene* in the Balkans and the Republic of Moldova. The confirmed locality on Mount Pashtrik is indicated by a green dot. Pale yellow dots represent other records from the Balkans derived from GBIF, Observado, published references, personal observations and information provided by L. Pamperis. Red dots denote historical but unconfirmed records from Romania and the Republic of Moldova, supplied by Székely Levente.

Conclusions

Kirinia climene (Esper, [1783]) is confirmed as an extant component of the Albanian fauna based on two recent records: a first recent observation near Lake Prespa in 2023 and a second locality on Mount Pashtrik in 2025, the latter confirming persistence at the historical site after more than a century. In the most recent Albanian Red List ([url](#)), the species is classified as Vulnerable (VU), reflecting the fact that, despite surveys conducted during the optimal flight period, additional localities have proven difficult to detect. Occurring at the western margin of its distribution in Albania, *K. climene* is considered particularly susceptible to local environmental conditions and the potential impacts of climate change.

Given the continuity of suitable habitat across the border, the occurrence of *K. climene* on the Kosovar side of Mount Pashtrik would not be unexpected.

The review of regional data shows a highly uneven distribution pattern across the Balkans, with strongholds in eastern Serbia and northern Greece, contrasted by fragmented or poorly documented populations in neighbouring regions. Historical records from Romania (Banat) and the Republic of Moldova lack recent confirmation, suggesting possible local extinction or severe under-recording. In contrast, populations in Serbia, Bulgaria, Greece, and parts of North Macedonia indicate that the species persists in suitable habitats across the southern Balkans, particularly in mountainous and karstic landscapes. Overall, the updated synthesis highlights both the persistence of *K. climene* in key refugial areas and substantial gaps in current knowledge, underlining the importance of continued faunistic surveys in the Balkans and adjacent regions.

Given the species' low detectability, resulting from its behaviour, habitat preferences and superficial resemblance to *Maniola jurtina* (Linnaeus, 1758), additional localities will likely be discovered in the Balkans. Likewise, hope remains that overlooked populations may yet be found in Romania and the Republic of Moldova.

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